

Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography

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The *Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography* includes over 300 selected English-language articles, books, and technical reports about academic libraries' digital publishing programs. While academic libraries have published a variety of digital publications, this bibliography primarily covers the open access publishing of scholarly books, journals, and other serials. The bibliography provides a brief overview of the early development of these publishing efforts. It covers library publishing from 1989 through 2022, the establishment of new university presses by academic libraries, especially all-digital open access presses, and the merger or cooperative efforts of libraries and university presses. It also covers the technical publishing infrastructures used by library publishing programs. It includes full abstracts for works under certain Creative Commons Licenses. Use the [PDF version](#) of this bibliography for printing (52 pages).

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[Introduction](#) ↑

This is the Library Publishing Coalition's [definition of library publishing](#):

The LPC defines library publishing as the set of activities led by college and university libraries to support the creation, dissemination, and curation of scholarly, creative, and/or educational works.

Generally, library publishing requires a production process, presents original work not previously made available, and applies a level of certification to the content published, whether through peer review or extension of the institutional brand.

Based on core library values, and building on the traditional skills of librarians, it is distinguished from other publishing fields by a preference for Open Access dissemination as well as a willingness to embrace informal and experimental forms of scholarly communication and to challenge the status quo.

Starting in the late 1980's, academic libraries were among the first publishers of digital books, journals, and other serials on the Internet. Some librarians and library associations also published digital journals and serials during this period. Here are a few examples of early digital book, journal, and serial projects.

With the approval and sponsorship of Robin N. Downes, the Director of the University of Houston Libraries, [The Public-Access Computer Systems Review](#), was launched in August 1989, with the [first issue](#) being published in January 1990. It had librarian editors and an international editorial board. It was distributed at no charge as ASCII e-mail messages on [PACS-L](#), UH's popular LISTSERV discussion list. Authors retained the copyright to *PACS Review* articles, and they gave the University of Houston the nonexclusive right to publish the articles in the journal and in future publications. Authors could republish their articles elsewhere, but they agreed to mention prior publication of the articles in the *PACS Review* within these works. Copying of *PACS Review* articles was permitted for educational, noncommercial use by academic computer centers, individual scholars, and libraries. The journal became refereed in November 1991.

Again with Downes' sponsorship, the University of Houston Libraries began publishing the [Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography](#), an open access book, in October 1996. This digital book was updated 64 times between 1996 and 2006 (Digital Scholarship continued its publication though [version 80](#) in 2011).

The Virginia Tech University Libraries' Scholarly Communications Project, which was founded in 1989, had an active digital publishing program in the 1990s. Gail McMillan describes the activities of this project as of 1999 in "[Digital Content: The Scholarly Communications Project](#)."

One of the initial activities of the SCP in 1989 was to determine how to publish an electronic journal. By the time the first issue its ejournal was ready in the fall of 1990, a desktop computer was rigged to also be a Gopher server and the *Journal of the International Academy of Hospitality Research* was available as an ASCII (text-only) file. In the ensuing years the SCP migrated its first four ejournals to the Web and added another 16 titles to its publication roster. Seventeen are the Web equivalent of printed academic journals that have been enhanced by hot links and 24-hour access. . . 15 titles are currently available with two more under development. Nine are electronic-only journals. Eight of the 15 current titles are edited by Virginia Tech faculty and two by faculty at other universities. All are associated with scholarly societies or professional associations; and four are mirrored for MIT Press.

In 1995, the SCP established [VPIEJ-L](#), an important LISTSERV discussion list about e-publishing issues.

The Stanford University Libraries established the HighWire Press in 1995. In "[The HighWire Press at Stanford University: A Review of Current Features](#)," Michael Newman

describes the origin of the press:

Three years ago, the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (ASBMB) was searching for alternatives for delivery of the society's journal, the *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (JBC). With over 30,000 pages per year and steady growth, the journal was outgrowing its printed format. A CD-ROM version had been introduced but had not been successful, in part because JBC is simply too large for CD-ROM. Robert Simoni, an editor of JBC, discussed the problem with Michael Keller, the Director of Stanford University Libraries, and after negotiations with ASBMB, the Stanford University Libraries enthusiastically agreed to take on development of the web version of JBC. The HighWire Press team, a unit within Stanford University Libraries, was appointed in early 1995. The first web version of JBC was released in May of that year.

In 1995, the University of Abertay, Dundee Library and UKOLN (the UK Office for Library and Information Networking) established *Ariadne*, a digital/print serial. Among the [its objectives](#) were:

- disseminating relevant news of JISC-funded information services and eLib developments to the UK HE community, and especially to those people working within library and computer centres. A movement is underway to converge such services, increasingly resulting in separate library/computing facilities being replaced by one "Information Resource Centre" in each University; the people in these centres form Ariadne's core audience.
- informing the target audience of a wide range of up to date and relevant concepts, resources and technologies, in the fields of electronic library research, networking and the use of IT in HE and libraries. This would be through resource and service reviews, interviews with key library or information science people, training tips, commissioned articles and regular columnists.. . .
- "newsy-ness". Ariadne is not a peer-reviewed journal. Instead, its nature sits somewhere between a newsletter and a magazine, with a much shorter article turn-around time than a journal. For example, most of the articles in the Web version are processed and made public within 2 or 3 weeks of the editor receiving such material.

Several academic libraries published digital serials in the 1990s, including:

[Current Cites](#) (Library Technology Watch Program at University of California, Berkeley Library, 1990)

[Public-Access Computer Systems News](#) (University of Houston Libraries, 1990)

In 1996, the The University of California, San Francisco Library and Center for Knowledge Management and the University of California Press [collaborated to publish a digital book](#): *The Cigarette Papers*. It was based on a print edition published by the UC Press. The print edition provided "a comprehensive analysis of internal documents from the Brown and Williamson Tobacco Company, the nation's third largest cigarette manufacturer." The book was based on papers that had been given anonymously to the library, which, after a legal dispute, the library "scanned, indexed, and published 8,000 pages on the Internet," and it then made a CD ROM version available for sale. Access to the digital book was as follows:

Released in July 1996 the Internet version. . . supports direct linkages from the text to the Brown and Williamson documents referenced in the book. The ability to search on each word in the text offers much broader access to the content than through the index of the paper product. In essence, the linkages offer readers immediate access to the same primary source material used by the authors in writing the book. The preface and first chapter have unrestricted access to permit potential subscribers to review the product prior to purchase. For those wanting to enter a subscription, the web address provides an order form and further information about the product.

Early digital journals published by academic librarians included:

Arachnet Electronic Journal on Virtual Culture (Diane Kovacs, Ralph Papakhian, and Ermel Stepp; 1993)

Information Research (Tom D. Wilson, 1995)

The Katharine Sharp Review (Kevin Ward, 1995)

LIBRES (earliest available issue is from 1992)

MC Journal: The Journal of Academic Media Librarianship (Lori Widzinski and Terrence McCormack, 1993)

Academic librarians led library association digital journal and serial publishing efforts during this period:

Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship (Harry LLull, Science and Technology Section of the Association of College and Research Libraries, 1991)

The Newsletter on Serials Pricing Issues (Marcia Tuttle, ALA Publisher/Vendor-Library Relations Committee, Resources and Technical Services Division, 1989)

Telecommunications Electronic Reviews (Tom Wilson, Library Information Technology Association, 1994)

See the *Directory of Electronic Journals, Newsletters and Academic Discussion Lists*, 6th edition and section 3.1 Electronic Serials: Case Studies and History of the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography* for further information about early e-journals and e-serials.

In the 1990's, digital journal and serial publishing projects that involved university libraries working in partnership arrangements included:

BioOne Project (the University of Kansas, the Big 12 Plus Libraries Consortium, and other partners)

Project Euclid (Cornell University Library and Duke University Press)

Project Muse (Johns Hopkins University Press and the Milton S. Eisenhower Library)

RLG DigiNews (the Research Libraries Group and the Cornell University Library Department of Preservation and Conservation)

Academic libraries acted as important digital journal publishing testing grounds for scholarly publishers in the 1990's including the following projects:

CORE Project

PEAK project

Red Sage Project

SuperJournal Project

TULIP Project.

See section 3.3 Electronic Serials: Electronic Distribution of Printed Journals of the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography* for further information on this topic.

In the last 20 years, there has been a growing movement by academic and other libraries to directly publish books, journals, and other works. This resurgent activity has been fueled by the open access movement, which is typically viewed as starting with the 2002

Budapest Open Access Initiative. Academic libraries built organizational and technical infrastructure to support this movement, often using open source software that was created in order to advance it. An increasing commitment to the OA movement sparked important cultural changes in libraries, which resulted in the proliferation of institutional repositories, scholarly communication units, and research data support units supported by them.

Discussing the library publishing landscape in 2017, [Janneke Adema and Graham Stone](#) said:

By late 2007, the American Research Libraries (ARL) had commissioned a survey of its membership finding that 44% of the 80 respondents were engaged in delivering 'publisher services' and 21% were currently planning developments; if smaller universities and colleges were taken into account the number is likely to have been higher (Xia, 2009). Hahn (2008) indicates that 88% of those that offered publishing services were publishing journals and 71% were publishing monographs — many of these were library-press collaborations. 79% also reported publishing conference proceedings. By 2013, an Association of American University Presses (AAUP) survey found that 65% of the 83 respondents regarded library publishing as increasingly important and 62% of all respondents (7% of library respondents) felt that it should be a core aim of the library's mission (AAUP, 2013).

The best snapshot of current academic libraries publishing activities is provided by the Library Publishing Coalition Directory Committee's *Library Publishing Directory 2022*. The introduction summarizes the findings of the survey that the directory is based on. Each entry provides detailed information about the library's publishing program, such as types of publications, funding, staffing, publishing platform, digital preservation strategy, and open access focus.

Open source software from the [Public Knowledge Project](#), such as [Open Journal Systems](#), is frequently used in library-based publishing programs; however, a variety of software tools are also employed. The Library Publishing Coalition's 2022 directory reports that: "OJS (47%), bepress [Digital Commons] (32%), DSpace (29%), Omeka (23%), Pressbooks (23%) and WordPress (25%) appear as the most heavily used platforms, while 13% of library publishers report using locally developed platforms." Promising new open source publishing programs include [Fulcrum](#), [Hypothesis](#), [Janeway](#), [Manifold](#), and [PubPub](#). See *Mind the Gap: A Landscape Analysis of Open Source Publishing Tools and Platforms* for a lengthy list of tools.

University presses are in a period of change and restructuring. Increasingly, they are being put under the administrative control of university libraries. Furthermore, entirely new all-digital open access university presses are being established, often under the direction of or in partnership with university libraries.

Paul Ayris and Lara Speicher provide a case study of a new open access university press in "[UCL Press: the UK's 'First Fully Open Access' University Press](#)."

Janneke Adema and Graham Stone provide a detailed overview of new university presses in the UK in *Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing*.

Coverage ↑

The *Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography* primarily covers published articles and books about the digital scholarly publishing activities of academic libraries since the late 1980's, especially their open access publishing activities. Its focus is on the publication of digital scholarly books, journals, and other serials. Some included works may treat a broader scope of academic library digital publishing activities. Readers interested in

detailed coverage of data publication issues may find the author's *Research Data Publication and Citation Bibliography* helpful.

With a few exceptions, this bibliography does not include editorials, e-mail messages, interviews, letters to the editor, presentation slides or transcripts, unpublished e-prints, or weblog postings. Coverage of conference papers and technical reports is very selective. Commercial software and other specialized software used by university presses are not covered by this bibliography.

Most sources have been published from January 2000 through December 2022; however, a limited number of earlier key sources are also included. The bibliography has links to included works. Such links are subject to change. Where possible, this bibliography uses Digital Object Identifier System (DOI) URLs.

Abstracts are included in this bibliography if a work is under a Creative Commons Attribution License (BY and national/international variations), a Creative Commons public domain dedication (CC0), or a Creative Commons Public Domain Mark and this is clearly indicated in the work (see the "Note on the Inclusion of Abstracts" below for more details).

This bibliography uses links to the Internet Archive for works that are not currently available from their publishers.

Dedication ↑

In memory of [Paul Evan Peters](#) (1947-1996), founding Executive Director of the Coalition for Networked Information, whose visionary leadership at the dawn of the Internet era fostered the development of scholarly electronic publishing.

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In June 1989, the University of Houston Libraries established The Public-Access Computer Systems Forum (PACS-L), a LISTSERV-based e-mail discussion list. This list was intended to foster dialog about issues related to the transition from the automation back-room library functions, such as acquisitions, cataloging, and serials control, to a new generation of electronic information systems that could be used directly by patrons. PACS-L covered topics such as the replacement of physical card catalogs with online catalogs, the use of index and abstract CD-ROM workstations, and provision of locally mounted index and abstract databases. In August 1989, University of Houston Libraries launched *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review*, one of the first scholarly e-journals on the Internet. It was freely available, allowed authors to retain their copyrights, had special copyright provisions for noncommercial use, and had a distinguished international editorial team. Issues were announced via e-mail on PACS-L, and articles were distributed as ASCII files from PACS-L's LISTSERV. Since commercial publishers were not even experimenting with electronic journals at this time, this journal, like other early open access journals on the Internet, had to grapple with a number of challenging editorial, format, procedural, policy, and technical issues and, in essence, help invent electronic journal publishing. At this time, the Internet was a collection of imperfectly interconnected independent networks primarily used by academics and other researchers solely for noncommercial purposes and many users of the journal were new to it and its associated technologies, such as e-mail.

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The *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography (SEPB)* is an electronic book that currently presents citations for over 1,400 selected English-language articles, books, and other printed and electronic sources that are useful in understanding scholarly electronic publishing efforts on the Internet. Most sources have been published between 1990 and the present; however, a limited number of key sources published prior to 1990 are also included. Where possible, links are provided to sources that are freely available via the Internet. There is no charge for accessing the bibliography.

The first version of the bibliography was published as an article in *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review* (an e-journal) in 1992. It was followed by a part-two article in 1994. These two articles were then used as the basis for a new bibliography article, "Network-Based Electronic Publishing of Scholarly Works: A Selective Bibliography," which was updated 25 times. In 1996, this bibliography was transformed into an electronic book.

SEPB includes "Scholarly Electronic Publishing Resources," a selective directory of related Web sites, and the "Scholarly Electronic Publishing Weblog," a frequently updated list of new publications and other resources that may be of interest to bibliography readers. The bibliography can be searched using Boolean operators.

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INTRODUCTION This paper explores the variability in self-identifying practices of academic libraries engaged in journal publishing and hosting activities. We were interested in how libraries characterized their efforts in this area and looked at whether there is an unspoken threshold for differentiation with respect to publishing-support naming conventions. **METHODS** Using the Library Publishing Directory, in-depth interviews, and a more widely circulated follow-up survey, the research team examined service offerings, divisions of responsibility, funding, terminology, and semantic associations within publishing, both as an active practice and as an advertised service. **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION** We aimed to tease out whether there was any sort of tipping point, or inferred rules, around when an institution chose to call the activity either publishing or hosting. We found no particular service, set of services, funding structure, or division of labor that obviously influenced the use of a particular term. Rather than noting a divide between publishing and hosting, participants spoke of both a spectrum and a tiering of work and support, though all emphasized that these models did not describe the quality of the work produced. This paper also discusses how use of the term library publishing creates additional ambiguity in naming practices, and considers some implications for library staff newly immersed in scholarly publishing work.

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Only a fairly narrow band of the scholarly output of a university finds a home with commercial publishers or university presses. From niche journals to conference proceedings to technical manuals to monographs with small disciplinary audiences, much of the rest of this work struggles to find a sustainable dissemination strategy. Library

publishing operations have stepped into this gap, particularly by offering their services to host small journals and other content based around institutional repositories. This work is often done as inexpensively as possible, with limited, targeted publishing services that just get the job done.

This model tends to break down when a library publisher tries to start doing books. Expectations around design and branding are higher, there is probably no established copyediting process such as a journal run by an external editorial board might already have, and print is often a necessity. It takes a different sort of workflow, and potentially quite a lot more production work, to publish books than it does to publish Open Access journals.

To solve this problem, Michigan Publishing Services has developed both a house service publishing imprint, Maize Books, and a white-labeled book publishing program, branded by University units, all running on the same technical and financial infrastructure. With an emphasis on Open Access with flexible Creative Commons licensing and affordable Print on Demand and EBook options combine workflow efficiencies with a menu of chargeback services to cover the costs of their production and allow staffing to be scaled to meet emerging needs.

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The authors, who all have experience with academic publishing, outline the landscape of new university and academic-led open access publishing, before discussing four interrelated sets of challenges which are often referred when questioning the viability of such publishing ventures. They are: (1) professionalism, (2) scale, (3) quality, and (4) discoverability & dissemination. The authors provide examples of how, albeit differing in size, form and ambition, these new presses are not just adhering to conventional publishing norms but often innovating in order to surpass them.

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Dishman, Cath. "Developing an Open Journals Hosting Service: A Case Study from Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU)." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 20, no. 2 (2017): 85-91. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.357>

The rise of the concept of 'library as publisher' has caused many university libraries to consider their role in the world of open access (OA) publishing and how that supports digital scholarship at their institutions. This paper outlines Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU) Library Services' first steps into that world through the offering of an open journals hosting service. It begins by explaining the background and justification for the library offering such a service and details the pilot undertaken to test the chosen system, Open Journal Systems (OJS). It considers what policies, procedures and support need to be in place in order to run a successful open journals hosting service. Lessons learned and observations gathered during the pilot are shared to help others considering setting up an open journals hosting service in their own institution. Finally it looks at the next steps for LJMU in taking this pilot forward to a full service offer.

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Donahoe, Diana R. "Libraries as Publishers: Implementing the Vision at the Georgetown Law Library." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.206>

TeachingLaw.com, an online, interactive textbook, created by a Georgetown law professor and published through the Georgetown Law Library, is used nationally by legal research and writing professors, law librarians, and others to teach first-year LRW courses, upper-class research classes, advanced writing courses, and LLM courses. It is divided into three sections—Legal Research, Legal Writing, and Grammar & Citation—and contains student tools, study aid material, quizzes, self-assessments, annotated sample documents, video testimonials, and other interactive material to teach students legal research strategies and writing techniques. It is updated twice a year to address upgrades to the three major legal research platforms (Westlaw, Lexis, and Bloomberg Law) and advances in the legal profession.

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How can a library publishing service with limited resources help editorial teams of peer-reviewed journals in their work? This paper focuses on the technical aspects of the peer review workflow that, if set up and adhered to properly, can contribute to improving the standard of the peer review process—and to some degree also the quality of peer review. The discussion is based on the work done at Septentrio Academic Publishing, the institutional service provider for open access publishing at UiT The Arctic University of Norway.

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Essmiller, Kathy, and Tataleni Asino. "Will Academic Library Publishing Break OER? A Diffusion of Innovations Study." *Journal of Interactive Media in Education* 2021, no. 1 (2021): p.24. <http://doi.org/10.5334/jime.673>

Academic libraries are among the organizations advocating for open educational resources (OER), often playing a key campus role in education, advocacy, and support of their creation and publication. Publication of OER resonates with the role of the academic library. Because "incongruence in perceptions" (Chtena 2019: 24) can cause difficulties and unforeseen challenges with implementation and use of OER, organizations involved in OER initiatives need familiarity with how OER and organizational values align. The goal of this exploration was to investigate how academic libraries enact academic library publishing programs and the ramification that has in the diffusion process of OER in higher education. Data collected in this single case study research project was analyzed through the lens of Diffusion of Innovations Theory. The findings from the study suggest that, if academic libraries are to enact the creation and publication of OER in ways appropriate to their conception, those involved will need to be intentional about ensuring enactment of the values foundational to OER. Future suggested research includes a multiple-case study comparative research study looking at academic library publication of OER, exploration of how opinion leaders and attributes of innovations impact academic library publication of OER, and investigation into the impact of organizational structure on the diffusion of OER creation and publication.

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Eve, Martin Paul. "Tear It Down, Build It Up: The Research Output Team, or the Library-as-publisher," *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 25, no. 2 (2012): 158-62. <http://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.25.2.158>

The solution that I propose to this growing crisis for all three stakeholders in the world of scholarly publishing lies in the concept of the Research Output Team (ROT), a fusion of the library and the publisher.⁴ In many ways this is a return to the idea of the university press; an in-house facility for publishing work. However, in the new open access environment, the overheads of printing and warehousing can be avoided, making the enterprise financially sound. This mode averts the financial problems in a way that the current pay-to-publish model cannot. Allow me to paint an initial picture of how this would work, including its fiscal viability and transition strategy. It must be stressed that this is not a complete model. It is a regulative concept designed to show an emergent feasibility that will either be developed, or be rendered unnecessary through auto-disciplinary publisher practices. Of course, the resultant outcome is a choice, or a gamble, for the industry itself to make.

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Farley, Kevin. "A Foray into Library Digital Publishing: The British Virginia Project at Virginia Commonwealth University." In *Too Much Is Not Enough: Charleston Conference Proceedings, 2013*, ed. Beth R. Bernhardt, Leah H. Hinds, and Katina P. Strauch, 501-504. Purdue University Press, 2014. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt6wq772.91>.

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Fenlon, Katrina S. "Understanding the Needs of Scholars in a Contemporary Publishing Environment." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.219>

We report on preliminary results of an ongoing investigation of humanities scholars' objectives and needs related to library publishing services and platforms.

Our multi-modal study informs the overarching project, "Publishing Without Walls: Understanding the Needs of Scholars in a Contemporary Publishing Environment," a Mellon-funded digital scholarly publishing initiative at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. The Publishing Without Walls project (PWW) aims to build capacity for participation in innovative publishing initiatives by scholars across the digital divide, and for scholars participating in a multi-institutional research consortium. At the same time, the project will develop a library-based scholarly publishing service model, which prioritizes scholar-driven, openly accessible, scalable, and sustainable scholarly communication practices.

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Fenlon, Katrina, Megan Senseney, Maria Bonn, and Janet Swatscheno. "Humanities Scholars and Library-Based Digital Publishing: New Forms of Publication, New Audiences, New Publishing Roles." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 50, no. 3 (2019): 159-182. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.50.3.01>

Fruin, Christine. "Organization and Delivery of Scholarly Communications Services by Academic and Research Libraries in the United Kingdom: Observations from across the Pond." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 5, no. 1 (2017): eP2157. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2157>

INTRODUCTION The U.K. library community has implemented collaborative strategies in key scholarly communication areas such as open access mandate compliance, and U.S. librarians could benefit from learning in greater detail about the practices and experiences of U.K. libraries with respect to how they have organized scholarly communication services. **METHODS** In order to better understand the scholarly communication activities in U.K. academic and research libraries, and how U.S. libraries could apply that experience in the context of their own priorities, an environmental scan via a survey of U.K. research libraries and in-person interviews were conducted. **RESULTS** U.K. libraries concentrate their scholarly communication services on supporting compliance with open access mandates and in the development of new services that reflect libraries' shifting role from information consumer to information producer. **DISCUSSION** Due to the difference in the requirements of open access mandates in the U.K. as compared to the U.S., scholarly communication services in the U.K. are more focused on supporting compliance efforts. U.S. libraries engage more actively in providing copyright education and consultation than U.K. libraries. Both U.K. and U.S. libraries have developed new services in the areas of research data management and library publishing. **CONCLUSION** There are three primary takeaways from the experience of U.K. scholarly communication practitioners for U.S. librarians: increase collaboration with offices of research, reconsider current organization and delegation of scholarly communication services, and increase involvement in legislative and policy-making activity in the U.S. with respect to access to research.

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During the last years, dramatic changes in the electronic publishing landscape have created new roles and changed the traditional ones. Presently, some libraries have capitalised on their experience and knowledge in information technology and electronic publishing to undertake such activities, while at the same time they spearhead the campaign for Open Access spreading within academic communities. The Library & Information Centre (LIC) of the University of Patras (UoP), Greece, has been playing an active role in promoting Open Access (OA) in Greece. Since 2007, LIC has been experimenting with OA publishing practices and tools within the framework of various R&D projects. Two of the major results of these efforts are the 'Pasiithe' e-publishing platform and the 'Dexamene' digital archive for Greek scholarly journals. Both platforms are based on OJS—Open Journal Systems e-publishing software. The two facilities were appropriately modified to meet the LIC's publishing and archiving requirements respectively. Currently two journals are being hosted on each platform and all four are from the Humanities. The LIC is negotiating with more publishers and editorial teams to host their journals. In this article we focus on: -technical and managerial key issues of the development and operation phases, -services and procedures, -the business model, - technological, procedural and legal issues and problems that were encountered when working together with publishers, editors and authors, and -future plans for improving and upgrading our e-publishing services into an integrated institutional platform to cover all kinds of publications and data types (monographs, conference proceedings, teaching material, bulletins, magazines etc.). The article concludes with a succinct presentation of the Directory of Greek Digital Resources, a pilot infrastructure developed by the LIC which indexes and presents digital publishing initiatives in Greece and aims to become a formal registry of Greek scholarly resources in digital format.

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Harboe-Ree, Cathrine. "Just Advanced Librarianship: The Role of Academic Libraries as Publishers." *Australian Academic & Research Libraries* 38, no. 1 (2007): 15-25.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00048623.2007.10721264>

Hare, Sarah. "Library Publishers as Educators: Crafting Curriculum for Undergraduate Research Journals." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2296>

INTRODUCTION Library publishing programs continue to play an increasingly important role in educating their constituents. In particular, library publishers that support undergraduate student journals often provide guidance to students on both mechanical and conceptual issues related to publishing. This article presents a case study for developing a one-credit-hour course to support an undergraduate student journal publication, the Indiana University *Journal of Undergraduate Research (IUJUR)*, at Indiana University Bloomington. **DESCRIPTION OF COURSE** The course is offered every fall as a mechanism for onboarding about thirty new undergraduate editors. The course was developed and taught by a librarian and an undergraduate student in consultation with IU's Office of the Vice Provost for Undergraduate Education. Course curriculum touches on topics that scholarly communication and information literacy librarians alike can adapt for a variety of educational contexts, including authentic activities for understanding peer review models and applying publishing innovations. **ASSESSMENT** The article details both the formative and summative assessment strategies the instructor utilized to gauge student understanding of key publishing concepts. The summative assessment utilizes pre- and post-tests and extends previous library literature to evaluate students' actual understanding of publishing concepts in addition to their perceived understanding and confidence. **LIMITATIONS AND NEXT STEPS** The course curriculum will continue to grow and change in order to accommodate students' misconceptions and interests.

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Harley, Diane, ed. *The University as Publisher: Summary of a Meeting Held at UC Berkeley on November 1, 2007*. Berkeley: Center for Studies in Higher Education, 2008.
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Hawkins, Kevin S. "Achieving Financial Sustainability: Are We Asking the Wrong Questions?" *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.213>

While technology has made producing copies of digital content almost entirely free, there is no escaping that publishing, according to most definitions of the term, still requires time and money. Any publishing service offered by a library must find a way to achieve financial sustainability—that is, operate without losing money.

However, even "losing money" is a tricky concept, especially when taking into account varying definitions of operating expenses (overhead costs) under different models for auxiliary services. Libraries are by their very nature cost centers, providing services without the expectation of recovering revenue, and are usually part of larger organizations that similarly provide services under partial or full subsidies. While libraries are often comfortable with charging for convenience services and for services to those outside their

designed community of users, careful thought should be given to which costs a publishing service—or any new service—should be expected to recover.

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———. "Creating a Library Publishing Program for Scholarly Books: Your Options Are Limited." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2262>

Publishing programs in academic libraries vary in their scope, offerings, and business models. Despite the many forms that these programs take, I have argued in the past that various factors constrain the design of a start-up publishing operation. In this commentary, I discuss in greater depth the key questions to be addressed before establishing a library publishing program for scholarly books, arguing that the viable options are in fact quite limited.

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———. "The Evolution of Publishing Agreements at the University of Michigan Library." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1175. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1175>

Taking as an example an open-access journal with a single editor, this article discusses the various configurations of rights agreements used by the University of Michigan Library throughout the evolution of its publishing operation, the advantages of the various models, and the reasons for moving from one to another.

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Johnston, Chelsea, and Jason Boczar. "Scholarly Publishing Literacy at the University of South Florida Libraries: From Advising to Active Involvement." *Journal of Librarianship and*

INTRODUCTION Successful open access (OA) publishing in libraries requires careful guidance and organization. Support and services offered vary depending on available resources as well as the robustness of a library's publishing program. **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM** This article describes the connection between publishing services and scholarly publishing literacy through examples from the University of South Florida (USF) Libraries. The USF Libraries' OA publishing program includes journals, textbooks, conference proceedings, and more. Our program balances advocating for open access with advising for actions that serve our partners' goals. This invites trust, sustainable relationships, and opportunities for new work. **NEXT STEPS** At the USF Libraries, more work must be done to formally assess our efforts. Our program will also explore new ways to support the ethical standards expected of libraries by pursuing stronger policies on diversity and inclusion. Using everyday work to demonstrate best practices is a manageable way to strengthen scholarly publishing efforts. We hope to continue growing our services, empowering our partners, and exploring our roles as advisors and advocates.

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Kate, Lara. "The Library's Role in the Management and Funding of Open Access Publishing." *Learned Publishing* 28, no. 1 (2015): 4-8. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20150102>

Keener, Alix. "Library (Publishing) School: Training and Competencies for the New Publishing Professional." *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 17, no. 2 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0017.206>

Many universities today now have a library where staff are exploring the frontiers of open access publishing and digital services. Librarians and other staff employed at these libraries have a diverse range of skills that work in harmony to bring digital content to their users, skills that could be harnessed to focus on scholarly publishing. Accordingly, schools of library science and information, which offer education in both academic and public service, could be one potential place for those aspiring to publishing to receive an education. In this article, I attempt to identify some of the tensions between theory and practice that currently underscore the murkiness in choosing the best location for publishing education and training. Library or information school, and the breadth of both traditional and nontraditional skills it has to offer, is a substantial, long-term alternative to rushed weekend publishing intensives and pricey seminars.

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Keller, Alice. "Library Support for Open Access Journal Publishing: A Needs Analysis." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 28, no. 3 (2015): 19-31. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.256>

The aim of this study was to establish the role of academic libraries in the context of open access (OA) journal publishing, based on the perceived needs of the journals and/or their editors. As a study sample, 14 OA journals affiliated to the University of Zürich, Switzerland, were taken. They were very different in nature, ranging from well-established society journals to newly founded titles launched by dedicated individuals. The study comprised two approaches: a comprehensive journal assessment and subsequent editor interviews. The journal assessments evaluated the functionalities, ease of use, sustainability and visibility of the journal. The interviews were used to get additional background information about the journals and explore editors' needs, experiences and viewpoints. The results show that journals affiliated to publishing houses or libraries are technically well provided for. Unaffiliated journals offer fewer functionalities and display some unconventional features, often described as innovations by the editors. More resources—financial or human—is seen by nearly all editors as the most pressing need and as a limitation to growth. In comparison, IT/technical needs are mentioned much less often. The article also describes the launch of an Editors' Forum, an idea suggested by the editors and implemented by the library. This Forum offered further valuable insight into the potential role of libraries, but also specifically addressed several of the editors' needs as expressed in the interviews.

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Kim Wu, Somaly, and Heather McCullough. "First Steps for a Library Publisher: Developing Publishing Services at UNC Charlotte J. Murrey Atkins Library." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2, (2015): 76-86. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0016>

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Kopak, Rick, and Chia-Ning Chiang. "An Interactive Reading Environment for Online Scholarly Journals: The Open Journal Systems Reading Tools." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 25, no. 2 (2009): 114-124. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10650750910961910>

Kosavic, Andrea. "The York Digital Journals Project: Strategies for Institutional Open Journal Systems Implementations." *College & Research Libraries* 71, no. 4 (2010): 310-321. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl-36r1>

Koskinen, Kimmo, Markku Roinila, and Kati Pauliina Syvälahti. "Open Journal Systems as a Pedagogical Tool to Teach and Learn Scholarly Publishing: The Helsinki University Library Experience." *LIBER Quarterly* 31, no. 1 (2021): 1-17. <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10881>

Academic libraries play a pivotal role in promoting open science, providing essential services for opening research and education. The library has also a key role in increasing awareness of open educational resources and practices. Editori is an open journal service at the University of Helsinki designed with an educational focus, providing simultaneously a contribution to the rising trend of university-based and library-based publishing. We show how this service, based on Open Journal Systems (OJS), can be applied as a pedagogical tool for teaching scholarly publishing skills to university students. In 2019 Helsinki University Library initiated a pilot project together with the Working Seminar of Doctoral Programme in Philosophy, Arts and Society of the Arts Faculty of the University of Helsinki. We outline expected pedagogical outcomes from the project, relating to scholarly communication skills, report feedback from teachers and students and discuss implications for future service development. In sum, students and teachers found the Editori platform intuitive and easy to use, although the learning curve for course leaders was considered steep in the initial phase.

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Laitsch, Dan, Elizabeth Farley-Ripple, and Jenice View. "Challenges and Achievements in Founding an Open Access Journal on Educational Leadership and Research Use." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 10, no. 2 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2019v10n2a309>

Lawrence, Janna C. "Libraries as Journal Publishers." *Journal of Electronic Resources in Medical Libraries* 7, no. 3 (2010): 235-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15424065.2010.505516>

Lawson, Stuart. "Library Publishing Services: An Investigation into Open Access Publishing in Academic Libraries." University of Brighton, 2013. <http://eprints.rclis.org/25156/>

Lefevre, Julie, and Terence K. Huwe. "Digital Publishing from the Library: A New Core Competency." *Journal of Web Librarianship* 7, no. 2 (2013): 190-214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19322909.2013.780519>

Library Publishing Coalition Directory Committee. *Library Publishing Directory 2022*. Atlanta, GA: Library Publishing Coalition, 2022. https://librarypublishing.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Library-Publishing-Directory_2022_web.pdf

The eighth edition of the *Library Publishing Directory* provides a snapshot of the publishing activities of over 150 academic and research libraries, including information about the number and types of publications they produce, the services they offer authors, how they are staffed and funded, and their future plans. In documenting the breadth and depth of activities in this field, this resource aims to articulate the unique value of library publishing; to establish it as a significant and growing community of practice; and to raise its visibility within a number of stakeholder communities, including administrators, funding agencies, other scholarly publishers, librarians, and content creators.

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Library Publishing Coalition Ethical Framework Task Force. *An Ethical Framework for Library Publishing, Version 1.0*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia, 2018. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284316777>.

Library publishing is distinguished in part from other types of scholarly publishing by a focus on adherence to the values and ethics of librarianship. *An Ethical Framework for Library Publishing* supports good practice in this area by providing resources and guidance in a number of ethical areas of importance to library publishers. Version 1.0 (published July 2018) covers publishing practice; accessibility; diversity, equity, and inclusion; privacy and analytics; and academic and intellectual freedom.

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Library Publishing Coalition Professional Development Committee. *Library Publishing Competencies*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284317123>

This publication provides a list of skills and knowledge useful in the development and provision of publishing services in libraries, organized into three categories: publishing, program development and management, and teaching and consulting. It will support publishing programs in identifying essential skills and will help individuals in the field to identify their strengths and the areas in which they are interested in growing.

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Library Publishing Coalition Professional Development Committee. *Library Publishing Documentation Toolkit*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2021. https://librarypublishing.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/LPC_DocumentationToolkit2021_FINAL.pdf

The toolkit is organized in four sections. The first two sections, Getting Started with Documentation and Planning a Documentation Day, focus on preparing and creating a plan for your Documentation Day. The third section, Suggested Documentation Projects to Tackle, provides some ideas for the kinds of projects you can work on, broken down by scope (one person, small group, big picture). The final section, Sharing Documentation Beyond Your Institution, includes some things to consider to help you determine when/if you should share your documentation. It also provides information on sharing through the Library Publishing Coalition Shared Documentation Portal.

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Library Publishing Coalition Research Committee. *Library Publishing Research Agenda*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284317124>

This publication is an exploration of areas in which research is needed to support practice in the field of library publishing. The Research Agenda offers exploratory overviews of six topics (assessment, labor, accessibility, non-traditional research outputs, peer review, and partnerships), each of which includes a summary, potential research questions, and a list of relevant resources. This publication will be of interest to anyone conducting or interested in conducting research in the field.

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Lippincott, Sarah Kalikman. *Library as Publisher: New Models of Scholarly Communication for a New Era*. Los Angeles: ATG LLC (Media), 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.9944345>

———. "The Library Publishing Coalition: Organizing Libraries to Enhance Scholarly Publishing." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 29, no. 2 (2016): 186-191.
<http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.296>

Library-based publishing efforts are gaining traction in academic and research libraries across the world, primarily in response to perceived gaps in the scholarly publishing system. Though publishing is a new area of work for libraries, it is often a natural outgrowth of their existing infrastructure and skill sets, leveraging the institutional repository as publishing platform and repositioning librarians' skills as information managers. For decades, these initiatives were primarily ad hoc and local, limiting the potential for library publishing to effect significant change. In 2013, over 60 academic and research libraries collectively founded the Library Publishing Coalition (LPC), a professional association expressly charged with facilitating knowledge sharing, collaboration and advocacy for this growing field. This article offers an overview of library publishing activity, primarily in the US, followed by an account of the creation and mission of the LPC, the first professional association dedicated wholly to the support of library publishers.

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Lippincott, Sarah, and Katherine Skinner. "Accountability in the Knowledge Commons: Lessons from Next Generation Library Publishing and the 2022 Values and Principles Summit." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 35, no. 20 (2022): p.20.
<http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.588>

Values and principles provide a scaffold for community governance of the knowledge commons, engaging stakeholders in the construction of a system that encourages participants to adhere to a shared set of ethical and functional practices. This article introduces the FOREST Framework for Values-Driven Scholarly Communication, a toolkit and approach developed by the Next Generation Library Publishing project to assess a community or organization's alignment with scholarly values and principles. The article situates the FOREST Framework within the context of other initiatives advancing values-based scholarly communication and explains the importance of assessment mechanisms as a core element in governing an equitable and sustainable knowledge commons. It also synthesizes the findings of a half-day summit hosted in February 2022 that convened representatives of values-and-principles-based frameworks and initiatives in scholarly communication to strategize a collective future for these efforts.

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———. "Building a Community-Driven Organization to Advance Library Publishing." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 367-373. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013.
<http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Lovett, Julia A., and Andrée J. Rathemacher. "What Do Editors Want?: Assessing a Growing Library Publishing Program and Finding Creative Solutions to Unmet Needs." In *The Time Has Come . . . to Talk of Many Things: Charleston Conference Proceedings, 2019*, ed. Beth R. Bernhardt, Leah H. Hinds, Lars Meyer, and Katina P. Strauch, 282–85. Purdue University Press, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv33t5ggk.52>

Mattson, Mark, and Linda Friend "A Planning Perspective for Library Journal Publishing Services." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 30, no. 3 (2014): 178-191. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0005>

McCready, Kate, and Emma Molls. "Developing a Business Plan for a Library Publishing Program." *Publications* 6, no. 4 (2018): 42.

Over the last twenty years, library publishing has emerged in higher education as a new class of publisher. Conceived as a response to commercial publishing practices that have strained library budgets and prevented scholars from openly licensing and sharing their works, library publishing is both a local service program and a broader movement to disrupt the current scholarly publishing arena. It is growing both in numbers of publishers and numbers of works produced. The commercial publishing framework which determines the viability of monetizing a product is not necessarily applicable for library publishers who exist as a common good to address the needs of their academic communities. Like any business venture, however, library publishers must develop a clear service model and business plan in order to create shared expectations for funding streams, quality markers, as well as technical and staff capacity. As the field is maturing from experimental projects to full programs, library publishers are formalizing their offerings and limitations. The anatomy of a library publishing business plan is presented and includes the principles of the program, scope of services, and staffing requirements. Other aspects include production policies, financial structures, and measures of success.

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McIntyre, Gordon, Janice Chan, and Julia Gross. "Library as Scholarly Publishing Partner: Keys to Success." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 1 (2013): eP1091. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1091>

Many academic libraries are looking at new ways to add value when they deliver services to faculty, and one potential area where the library can provide new services is in partnering with academic staff to support the dissemination of faculty research. Librarians have traditionally helped faculty researchers at the beginning of the research cycle, with the discovery and delivery of information sources. However, they are now playing a role at the end of the research cycle, providing services that support scholarly publishing. This paper examines library participation in faculty-led publishing ventures. In particular, it explores the value that smaller research libraries can provide to faculty editors through journal hosting, which will be analysed through an examination of the successful migration of the *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, a faculty-administered journal at Edith Cowan University in Perth, Western Australia, to the University's institutional repository. This transition provided library staff members at Edith Cowan University opportunities to develop new knowledge and skills in journal publishing, while meeting the journal's need for a better way to manage a growing influx of article submissions. The resultant faculty-library partnership enabled more effective management of the journal and has contributed to its growing success. The evaluative framework developed to enable assessment of the success of this journal's transition can help other libraries demonstrate the success of their own journal hosting ventures.

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McKiernan, Gerry. "Scholar-Based Innovations in Publishing. Part II: Library and Professional Initiatives." *Library Hi Tech News* 20, no. 3 (2003): 19-27. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lhtn.2003.23920caf.004>

McMahon, Melody Layton. "The Library as Publisher? Is It Possible for a Small Library?" *Theological Librarianship* 8, no. 1 (2015): 4-6. <https://doi.org/10.31046/tl.v8i1.365>

McMillan, Gail. "Librarians as Publishers." *College & Research Libraries News* 61, no. 10 (2000): 928-931. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.61.10.928>

Melton, Sarah. "The Center That Holds: Developing Digital Publishing Initiatives at the Emory Center for Digital Scholarship." In *Laying the Foundation: Digital Humanities in Academic Libraries*, ed. John W. White and Heather Gilbert, 95–110. Purdue University Press, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt163t7kq>

Missingham, Roxanne, and Lorena Kanellopoulos. "University Presses in Libraries: Potential for Successful Marriages." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 30, no. 3 (2014): 158-166. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0001>

Molls, Emma J. "Assessing the Success of Library Published Journals." *Against the Grain* 31, no. 4 (2019): Article 13. <https://doi.org/10.7771/2380-176X.8414>

———. "Publishing Scholarly Societies: One Library's Approach." *The Serials Librarian* 82, no. 1-4 (2022): 194-198. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2022.2028505>

Moulaison, Heather Lea, and Anthony J. Million. "E-publishing in Libraries: The [Digital] Preservation Imperative." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2 (2015): 87-98. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0009>

Mullins, James L., Catherine Murray-Rust, Joyce L. Ogburn, Raym Crow, October Ivins, Allyson Mower, Daureen Nesdill, Mark Newton, Julie Speer, and Charles Watkinson. *Library Publishing Services: Strategies for Success: Final Research Report*. Washington, DC: SPARC, 2012. <https://libres.uncg.edu/ir/listing.aspx?id=17801>

Murphy, Aajay. "Functioning in the Grey: Kennesaw State University's Library Journal Publishing Projects." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.217>

The Digital Commons @ Kennesaw State University operates in the grey areas between publisher and repository, autonomous unit and library resource, facilitator and collector. Utilizing the Digital Commons, a Berkeley Electronic Press platform, Kennesaw State University has had some success with its various journal-publishing projects by encouraging faculty and student involvement. However, publishing existed in relatively uncontrolled and unstable ways prior to 2015. With the development of policies and procedures to streamline journal intake, start up, and execution, great strides have been made to tighten up the vision of the publishing wing without crossing over entirely into the terrain of university press.

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Nelson, Rebecca, and Becky Thoms. "The Practical and the Aspirational: Managing the Student Employee Experience in Library Publishing Efforts." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 9, no. 1 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.31274/jlsc.12913>

Student employees are a critical component in the workforce of academic libraries. While more established library services have the benefit of attracting student employees specifically interested in their work, scholarly communication programs, and library publishing efforts in particular, have more difficulty describing and garnering interest in their work. This article describes the journey of the Digital Initiatives Unit at Utah State University Libraries as we navigated the particular trials that come with library publishing—specifically delving into the work of our institutional repository (IR) and the role of student employees in those efforts. The labor of our program is variable and largely project-based, which has presented a number of challenges related to our student employees: understanding the larger context of their work; retention of knowledge and skills alongside their ability to prioritize; and a struggle to transfer skills from one project to another. Addressing these problems involved more intentional gathering of student feedback, colleague brainstorming, and trial and error; through which process and results we are gaining a more developed understanding of the critical importance of the student experience. When student employees see their work as more than just a job, and recognize the skills they are learning, they come away with greater satisfaction and our unit benefits from improved outputs. Using what we have learned, we will be able to continue our efforts for a better student experience as well as creating future goals for our unit.

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Newton, Mark P., Eva T. Cunningham, and Julie N. Morris. "Library Services: Planning for the Future of Scholarly Publishing." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 109-117. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013.

<http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Newton, Mark P., Eva T. Cunningham, and Kerri O'Connell. "Counting the Cost: A Report on APC-Supported Open Access Publishing in a Research Library." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1184.

<http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1184>

BACKGROUND At one-hundred twenty-two articles published, the open access journal *Tremor and Other Hyperkinetic Movements (Tremor)* is growing its readership and expanding its influence among patients, clinicians, researchers, and the general public interested in issues of non-Parkinsonian tremor disorders. Among the characteristics that set the journal apart from similar publications, *Tremor* is published in partnership with the library-based publications program at Columbia University's Center for Digital Research and Scholarship (CDRS). **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM** The production of *Tremor* in conjunction with its editor, a researching faculty member, clinician, and epidemiologist at the Columbia University Medical Center, has pioneered several new workflows at CDRS: article-charge processing, coordination of vendor services, integration into PubMed Central, administration of publication scholarships granted through a patient-advocacy organization, and open source platform development among them. Open access publishing ventures in libraries often strive for lean operations by attempting to capitalize on the scholarly impact available through the use of templated and turnkey publication systems. For CDRS, production on *Tremor* has provided opportunity to build operational capacity for more involved publication needs. The following report introduces a framework and account of the costs of producing such a publication as a guide to library and other non-traditional publishing operations interested in gauging the necessary investments. Following a review of the literature published to date on the costs of open access publishing and of the practice of journal publishing in academic libraries, the authors present a brief history of *Tremor* and a tabulation of the costs and expenditure of effort by library staff in production. **NEXT STEPS** Although producing *Tremor* has been more expensive than other partner publications in the center's portfolio, the experiences have improved the library's capacity for addressing more challenging projects, and developments for *Tremor* have already begun to be applied to other journals.

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Oberlander, Cyril. "Textbooks and Educational Resources in Library-Based Publishing." In *Getting the Word Out: Academic Libraries as Scholarly Publishers*, ed. Maria Bonn and Mike Furlough, 177-192. Chicago: Association of College and Research Libraries, 2015.

https://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org.acrl/files/content/publications/booksanddigitalresources/digital/9780838986981_getting_OA.pdf

O'Donnell, Daniel Paul, Carey Viejou, Sylvia Chow, Rumi Graham, Jarret McKinnon, Dorothea Morrison, Reed Parsons, Courtney Rieger, Vanja Spirić, Elaine Toth, Kimberly M. Dohms, Paul Esau Wilfrid, Steve Firth, and Kayla Ueland. "Zombie Journals: Designing a Technological Infrastructure for a Precarious Journal." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 9, no. 2 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2018v9n2a296>.

Okerson, Ann, and Alex Holzman. *The Once and Future Publishing Library*. Washington, DC: CLIR, 2015. <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub166/>

Park, Ji-Hong, and Jiyoun Shim. "Exploring How Library Publishing Services Facilitate Scholarly Communication." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 43, no. 1 (2011): 76-89.

<https://doi.org/10.1353/scp.2011.0038>

Pate, Jennifer, and Elaine Thornton. "OER Publishing and Libraries." *The Serials Librarian*, 82, no. 1-4 (2022): 150-153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2022.2018237>

Perry, Anali Maughan, Carol Ann Borchert, Timothy S. Deliyannides, Andrea Kosavic, Rebecca Kennison, and Sharon Dyas-Correia. "Libraries as Journal Publishers." *Serials Review* 37, no. 3 (2011): 196-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2011.10765382>

Pitcher, Kate. "Library Publishing of Open Textbooks: The Open SUNY Textbooks Program." *Against the Grain* 26, no. 5 (2014): Article 10. <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/atg/vol26/iss5/10/>

Raju, Reggie, Jill Claassen, and Lena Nyahodza. "Library Publishing for an Inclusive Education." In *Humanizing LIS Education and Practice*, ed. Keren Dali, Nadia Caidi, 145-57. Abington, Oxon: Routledge, 2020. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/1196177448>

Raju, Reggie, Jill Claassen, Jeremiah Pietersen, and Danielle Abrahamse. "An Authentic Flip Subscription Model for Africa: Library as Publisher Service." *Library Management* 41, no. 6/7 (2020): 369-381. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-03-2020-0054>

Raju, Reggie, and Jeremiah Pietersen. "Library as Publisher: From an African Lens." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.203>

Africa is trapped in two paradoxical situations. The first is that the production of research is dependent on access to research—African researchers have been hamstrung by limited access to relevant and authentic scholarly literature to support the growth in their research output. It has been mooted that the saviour is improved access to open content. This gives rise to the second paradox—open access removes the financial barriers to the end user. In this new paradigm, the cash-cow for publishers is now the author via the payment of article processing charges (APCs). However, African researchers, in the main, cannot afford these exorbitant APCs, limiting their capacity to publish excellent research in leading international journals that have an OA publishing option.

Hence, it is incumbent on research intensive institutions on the African continent to take the lead in sharing scholarly output to engender and nurture a culture of research at those African institutions that are overwhelmed by low research output. To support the dissemination of trusted and relevant scholarly content, African libraries need to provide proactive 'library as publisher' services. These services must be delivered for non-profit purposes and must be underpinned by 'philanthropic-social justice' principles.

Some South African academic institutions, via their libraries, have stepped-up to the plate to make scholarly freely content accessible to both users and authors via suite of diamond open access services. The library as a publisher must gain traction quickly as a mainstream service provided by the higher education libraries in South Africa.

This paper will examine the new trend of library as a publisher from a developing world perspective. The benefits for the provision of 'library as publisher' service is colossal for development in the global South.

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Rayner, Sarah, and Desmond Coyle. "Books Right Here Right Now at the University of Manchester Library." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 29, no. 2 (2016): 172-180. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.309>

Books Right Here Right Now is a strategic project to radically change core text provision at the University of Manchester. In order to investigate new models for electronic textbook delivery, the project team are running a series of e-textbook pilots, providing textbooks directly to our students via the virtual learning environment.

This paper focuses on how usage data and the views of our students and academic staff are underpinning the project in terms of acquisition models, negotiations with publishers and providing a new product to our students. Having detailed the project findings, the article concludes with the authors' thoughts on the changing environment of the e-textbook

market and the various issues within the existing models of e-textbook provision, giving recommendations as to how academic libraries and publishers can help to shape a sustainable model for the UK.

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Reed, Marianne. "Sowing the Seeds of Journal Success: Cultivating Relationships with Journal Editors and Staff." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.218>

Since 2007, the University of Kansas Libraries has provided support to the KU community for the management and distribution of online scholarly journals and other publications, and currently hosts over 20 scholarly journals. While much of the literature about library publishing focuses on issues such as technical infrastructure, policies and processes, skills and training, or economic models—all important areas to address, to be sure—this presentation will focus on a less documented aspect of library-based publishing: building and maintaining relationships with journal editors and staff. This is often time consuming and hidden labor, but has been key to the ongoing viability of our program. Through regular and ongoing engagement with our journal partners we can keep abreast of their evolving needs, catch potential issues before they blossom into problems, and create goodwill and trust that we can tap into down the road when advocating to administrators about the value of the publishing program. We will share and discuss the various outreach and engagement efforts (successful and unsuccessful) that we have pursued, including regular meetings of our "Editors Forum," an email listserv for journal editors and staff, regular check-ins regarding journal operations, and coordinated efforts with related library initiatives such as open access and digital humanities. We will advocate for an intentional, multi-faceted approach to building relationships with journal editors as a key aspect of a sustainable publishing program.

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Richard, Jennifer, Denise Koufogiannakis, and Pam Ryan. "Librarians and Libraries Supporting Open Access Publishing." *Canadian Journal of Higher Education* 39, no. 3 (2009): 33-48. <http://journals.sfu.ca/cjhe/index.php/cjhe/article/view/474>

Riddle, Kelly. "Creating Policies for Library Publishing in an Institutional Repository: Exploring Purpose, Scope, and the Library's Role." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2 (2015): 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0007>

Robertson, Wendy C., and Charlene N. Simser. "Managing E-publishing: Perfect Harmony for Serialists." *Serials Librarian* 64, no. 1-4 (2013): 118-128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2013.760399>

Roh, Charlotte. "Library Publishing and Diversity Values: Changing Scholarly Publishing through Policy and Scholarly Communication Education." *College & Research Libraries News*, 77, no. 2 (2016): 82-85. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRLN.77.2.9446>

Roh, Charlotte, and Vanessa Gabler. "Systemic Barriers and Allyship in Library Publishing: A Case Study Reminder That No One Is Safe from Racism." *College & Research Libraries News* 81, no. 3 (2020): 141-144. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.81.3.141>

Roinila, Markku, and Juuso Ala-Kyyny. "Library Hosted Open Access Journals as Tools for Teaching Publishing Practices." *Journal of the European Association for Health Information and Libraries* 18, no. 2 (2022): 3-6. <https://doi.org/10.32384/jeahil18515>

We will discuss teaching publishing practices and different forms of student participation in three open access journals hosted by Helsinki University Library's Editori-service, two of which are from a field of neurosciences. As a theoretical framework, we will distinguish between classroom journals (with students providing the content and teacher acting as an editor), student-led journals (students acting in both roles) and mock journals (which are

like classroom journals, but the journal remains unpublished). Our discussion is founded on interviews of journal editors and analysis of student roles in the journals. In addition, we will mention one previous experiment of a mock journal in Editori-service, related to a Doctoral School working seminar in Humanities and Social Sciences.

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Royster, Paul. "Library Publishing Is Special: Selection and Eligibility in Library Publishing." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1183. <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1183>

Traditional publishing is based on ownership, commerce, paid exchanges, and scholarship as a commodity, while library activities are based on a service model of sharing resources and free exchange. I believe library publishing should be based on those values and should not duplicate or emulate traditional publishing. University presses have mixed views of library publishing, and libraries should not adopt those attitudes. Library publishers are not gatekeepers; their mission is dissemination. Libraries need to publish because traditional publishing suffers from high rejection rates, required surrender of intellectual property, long production schedules, high cost of products, and limited dissemination. Nebraska's Zea Books is a response to these needs. Miscellaneous advice for library publishers is offered and selection and eligibility criteria are outlined. A suggestion is made for a cooperative ebook distribution network.

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Sandy, Heather Moulaison, and Janice Bially Mattern. "Academic Library-Based Publishing: A State of the Evolving Art." *Library Trends* 67, no. 2 (2018): 337-357. <https://doi.org/10.1353/LIB.2018.0040>

Santiago, Ariana, and Lauren Ray. "Navigating Support Models for OER Publishing: Case Studies from the University of Houston and the University of Washington." *Reference Services Review* 48, no. 3 (2020): 397-413. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RSR-03-2020-0019>

Saunders, Richard L. "Where Do We Go From Here? Starting Up an Academic Journal In a Smaller Institution." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.209>

There is no reliable formula for starting or sustaining a scholarly journal. This essay encourages readers to develop and address sustainable editorial and publication processes, addressing five key elements that increase the likelihood that a journal can be successfully sustained over time. . . .

This essay illustrates decisions and opportunities which need definition when establishing and disseminating a viable scholarly journal. Each concern and issue should be considered and resolved; each decision will lead to other decisions as academic institutions once again transcend being merely warehouses for knowledge and become again disseminators of it. The comments here are drawn from lessons learned over several years working in the publishing industry and as an author myself. It is not a how-to guide, nor does it guarantee success. The observations are prompts intended to help librarians as would-be publishers think carefully. The goal for this article is not to encourage library publishing per se, but rather to help readers understand the moving parts involved in establishing a flexible, resilient process that can sustain a publication in the long term and independent of the personalities driving its creation. I presume that libraries will be required to start small and bootstrap their journals into existence, for the sort of investment capital start-up common to the tech and software industries is typically lacking in academia. I also presume that institutions will craft a scholarly journal rather than a trade journal or non-specialist magazine. Comments are grouped into five broad sections or processes for convenience. Key points are rendered in italics for convenience and clarity within paragraphs.

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Savenije, Bas, and Natalia Grygierczyk. "The Role and Responsibility of the University Library in Publishing in a University." *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries* 10, no. 3 (2000): 312-325. <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.7603>

As a consequence of developments in information technology, the traditional information chain is subject to change: the separate functions in this chain become more and more integrated and the roles played by the traditional parties are most uncertain. Several new models in scholarly publishing and communication are emerging, in which the scientific community and the scientists themselves play a central role. It is more than natural for universities to support these developments in order to realise new models of scientific communication that are more in tune with the needs of the academic community than the traditional model, which has led to a serious serials crisis. An important step in this direction is that each university encourages scientists to make more use of ICT in their research publications. However, it is also necessary to give serious attention to organisational matters: in this respect every university should take responsibility for collecting, archiving and disclosing the scientific output of its own scientists. The provision of scientific information is the traditional core business of university libraries and it is a natural extension of this role for university libraries to support this development and to organise the processes needed. The paper describes the role that universities and their libraries have to play. It also gives some examples of library initiatives in this field, including an evaluation of their impact on the innovation of scientific communication.

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Schlosser, Melanie. "Building Capacity for Academy-Owned Publishing through the Library Publishing Coalition." *Library Trends* 67, no. 2 (2018): 359-375. <https://doi.org/10.1353/LIB.2018.0041>

———. "Write Up! A Study of Copyright Information on Library-Published Journals." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 4 (2016). <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2110>

INTRODUCTION Libraries have a mission to educate users about copyright, and library publishing staff are often involved in that work. This article investigates a concrete point of intersection between the two areas—copyright statements on library-published journals. **METHODS** Journals published by members of the Library Publishing Coalition were examined for open access status, type and placement of copyright information, copyright ownership, and open licensing. **RESULTS** Journals in the sample were overwhelmingly (93%) open access. 80% presented copyright information of some kind, but only 30% of those included it at both the journal and the article level. Open licensing was present in 38% of the journals, and the most common ownership scenario was the author retaining copyright while granting a nonexclusive license to the journal or publisher. 9% of the sample journals included two or more conflicting rights statements. **DISCUSSION** 76% of the journals did not consistently provide accurate, easily-accessible rights information, and numerous problems were found with the use of open licensing, including conflicting licenses, incomplete licenses, and licenses not appearing at the article level. **CONCLUSION** Recommendations include presenting full copyright and licensing information at both the journal and the article level, careful use of open licenses, and publicly-available author agreements.

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Schmidt, Heidi, Karen Butter, and Cynthia Rider. "Building Digital Tobacco Industry Document Libraries at the University of California, San Francisco Library/Center for Knowledge Management." *D-Lib Magazine* 8, no. 9 (2002). <http://www.dlib.org/dlib/september02/schmidt/09schmidt.html>

Senseney, Megan, Maria Bonn, Christopher Maden, Janet Swatscheno, LaTasha Velez, Harriett Green, and Katrina Fenlon. "Informing Library-Based Digital Publishing: Selected Findings from a Survey of Scholars' Needs in a Contemporary Publishing Environment,"

Digital Scholarship in the Humanities, 34, issue supplement 1 (December 2019): i172-i178. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqy052>

Shuttleworth, Kate, Kevin Stranack, and Alison Moore. "Course Journals: Leveraging Library Publishing to Engage Students at the Intersection of Open Pedagogy, Scholarly Communications, and Information Literacy." *Partnership: The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research*. 14, no. 2 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.21083/partnership.v14i2.5339>

Simser, Charlene N., Marcia G. Stockham, Elizabeth Turtle. "Libraries as Publishers: A Winning Combination." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31 no. 2, (2015): 69-75. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0006>

Skinner, Katherine, and Sarah Lippincott. "Library Publishing Initiatives: North America." In *Encyclopedia of Library and Information Sciences*, 3rd ed., ed. Marcia J. Bates and Mary Niles Maack, 1-8. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2009. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/454373558>

Skinner, Katherine, Sarah Lippincott, Julie Speer, and Tyler Walters. "Library-as-Publisher: Capacity Building for the Library Publishing Subfield." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 17, no. 2 (2014). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0017.207>

Skinner, Katherine, Melanie Schlosser, Peter Berkery, Meredith Baab, Jasmine Mulliken, Friederike Sundaram, Dennis Lloyd, Mary Rose Muccie, Brenna McLaughlin, and John W. Warren. "Library Publishing Curriculum Textbook." *Library Publishing Curriculum* 1 (2021): Article 30. <https://digitalcommons.wayne.edu/libpubcurriculum/vol1/iss1/30>

In the original, modular curriculum (2018) on which this textbook is based, each unit of the Library Publishing Curriculum contained an instructor's guide, narrative, a slideshow with talking notes, bibliographies, supplemental material, and activities for use in a physical or virtual classroom for workshops and courses. This textbook version, produced in 2021, adapts the original narrative as the primary content (with very little additional editing) and incorporates the bibliographies, appendices, and images from the slideshow into a linear reading and learning experience for use by librarians or students learning on their own or as part of a classroom learning experience. The LPC hopes others use and extend this CC-BY version into even more learning opportunities to help create a more equitable publishing ecosystem.

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Sondervan, Jeroen, and Fleur Stigter. "Sustainable Open Access for Scholarly Journals in 6 Years —The Incubator Model at Utrecht University Library Open Access Journals." *Learned Publishing* 31, no. 3 (2018): 230-234. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1151>

Instead of steering towards another open access publishing venue, the Utrecht University Library developed a new strategy to support open access journal publishing – one that shifted our focus from hosting journals to the development of high-quality, peer reviewed journals, setting a 6-year period for them to implement a sustainable publishing model based on open access. The choice of 6 years was made because our experience has been that a journal is really on track only after 4 years. Then there are 2 more years to strengthen and develop the publication strategy. We divided the 6-year period into two parts. After an initial 3 years, there will be a contract renewal if things are going well, and we can adjust certain strategies and make new arrangements if required. If, however, we question the viability of the journal, the contract will be terminated at this point.

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Spiro, Lisa. "Nimble and Oriented towards Teaching and Learning Publishing Services at Small Academic Libraries." In *Getting the Word Out: Academic Libraries as Scholarly Publishers*, ed. Maria Bonn and Mike Furlough, 141-174. Chicago: Association of College and Research Libraries, 2015.

https://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org.acrl/files/content/publications/booksanddigitalresources/digital/9780838986981_getting_OA.pdf

Stone, Graham. "Huddersfield Open Access Publishing." *Information Services & Use* 31, no. 3-4 (2011): 215-223. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3233/ISU-2012-0651>

Stone, Graham, Kathrine Jensen, and Megan Beech. "Publishing Undergraduate Research: Linking Teaching and Research through a Dedicated Peer-Reviewed Open Access Journal." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 47, no. 2 (2016): 147-170. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.47.2.147>

Stranack, Kevin. "Sustaining Library Publishing through Multi-Stakeholder Cooperatives." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.216>

Library-based open access publishing continues to grow internationally, with a variety of economic models emerging to provide sustainable funding for the production and dissemination of high quality, peer-reviewed publications. Although author processing charges have become increasingly common, some library-based publishers are experimenting with cooperative structures where key stakeholders, including libraries, societies, funding agencies, and others come together to collectively fund and support publishing activities. This session will report on the MacArthur-funded Open Access Publishing Cooperative Study, which is investigating the viability of publishing cooperatives through an examination of pilot projects from around the world.

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Thomas, Sarah E. "Publishing Solutions for Contemporary Scholars: The Library as Innovator and Partner." *Publishing Research Quarterly* 22, no. 2 (2006): 27-37. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12109-006-0013-5>

Tracy, Daniel G. "Libraries as Content Producers: How Library Publishing Services Address the Reading Experience." *College & Research Libraries* 78, no. 2 (2017): 219-240. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.78.2.16583>

———. "The Users of Library Publishing Services: Readers and Access Beyond Open." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 18, no. 3 (2015). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0018.303>

Unsworth, John M. "Pubrarians and Liblishers at 20: Reflections on Library Publishing from 1995-2014." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1201. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1201>

Vandegrift, Micah, and Josh Bolick. "'Free to All': Library Publishing and the Challenge of Open Access." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1181. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1181>

There is a significant and important responsibility as libraries move into the role of publishing to retain our heritage of "access for all." Connecting and collaborating with colleagues in the publishing industry is essential, but should come with the understanding that the library as an organization is access-prone. This article discusses the complexities of navigating that relationship, and calls for libraries and publishers to embrace and respect the position from which we begin. Finally, the article forecasts several possible characteristics of what "publishing" might look like if libraries press the principle of access in this growing area.

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Waller, Jen, Cody Taylor, and Stacy Zemke. "From Start-up to Adolescence: University of Oklahoma's OER Efforts." In *OER: A Field Guide for Academic Librarians*, ed. Andrew

Wesolek, Jonathan Lashley, and Anne Langley, 351-379. Forest Grove, OR: Pacific University Press, 2018. <https://commons.pacificu.edu/pup/3>

We intend this book to act as a guide writ large for would-be champions of OER, that anyone—called to action by the example set by our chapter authors—might serve as guides themselves. The following chapters tap into the deep experience of practitioners who represent a meaningful cross section of higher education institutions in North America. It is our hope that the examples and discussions presented by our authors will facilitate connections among practitioners, foster the development of best practices for OER adoption and creation, and more importantly, lay a foundation for novel, educational excellence.

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Walters, Tyler. "The Future Role of Publishing Services in University Libraries Initiatives." *portal: Libraries and the Academy* 12, no. 4 (2008): 425-454. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2012.0041>

Watkinson, Charles. "The University as Publisher Revisited." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 27, no. 2 (2014): 181-185. <http://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.131>

This article explores the growing involvement of libraries in providing publishing services for the informal scholarly outputs traditionally referred to as 'gray literature'. By envisioning institutional repository (IR) infrastructure as a publishing platform, libraries can bring conference proceedings, technical reports, niche journals, white papers and other hard-to-source materials into the mainstream. The opportunities of such an approach for scholars, libraries and university presses open to collaboration are considered. Several directions for future expansion of this activity, such as the publication of student scholarship and the development of more formal products linked to gray literature, are suggested.

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Welzenbach, Rebecca A. "Journals Are People, Too: The Human Factor in Sustainable Journal Publishing Partnerships." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 145-152. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013. <http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Wipperman, Sarah L., Shawn Martin, and Chealsye Bowley. "Balancing Influence in a Shifting Scholarly Communication Landscape: Creating Library-Owned, Community-Aligned Infrastructure through Individual, Local, and Community Action." *College & Research Libraries News* 79, no. 5 (2018): 244-247. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRLN.79.5.244>

Wirth, Andrea A. "Distributed Publishers: Collaborating & Facilitating Publishing Across Campus." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.215>

While the support for publishing open access journals in libraries is widespread as evidenced by the Library Publishing Coalition member roster and discussions about journals on library listservs and at conferences, not all libraries approach journal support by taking on the role of "publisher." Local practices, policies, and the relationship of the library with the university provide guidance as to how a particular library and its campus address journal publishing.

But if not publisher, then what? Instead, libraries, recognizing implementing and sustaining a publishing program can be costly and daunting, have alternatives to consider. In one scenario, the library may act a journal "host" by collaborating and sharing expertise with faculty, students, and academic units that do wish to start a journal. As host, the library can provide critical services and technology for the campus-wide publishing enterprise, without assuming complete oversight for the journals that it supports. For example, the provision of a journal platform, technical expertise on the platform, and sharing expertise in the area of

scholarly publishing facilitate journal success. This approach, however, has both benefits and drawbacks.

The University of Nevada, Las Vegas (UNLV) Libraries act as journal host, in order to best utilize the available staffing around journal services and to help promote a sense of ownership in UNLV's academic units (which act as publishers). Using the UNLV model as an example, this presentation describes how journals are supported including an overview of what works well, what issues arise with distributed campus publishing, and takeaways for libraries who wish to support local journal publishing, but may not have the staffing and other resources to become a publisher.

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Wojturska, Rebecca. "Facilitating Student-Led Diamond Open Access Publishing in the Library," *Journal of the European Association for Health Information and Libraries* 18, no. 2 (2022): 7-10. <https://doi.org/10.32384/jeahil18516>.

Edinburgh Diamond is a book and journal hosting service, based in the University of Edinburgh's library. A free service for our staff and students, Edinburgh Diamond seeks to embolden and support those who wish to be involved with diamond open access publishing. Almost half of the journals we host are student-led publications. This article demonstrates why student-led open access publishing is important for student engagement, experiential learning, and academic literacy, and how the library helps facilitate that.

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Xia, Jingfeng. "Library Publishing as a New Model of Scholarly Communication." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 40, no. 4 (2009): 370-338. <https://doi.org/10.1353/scp.0.0052>

3.1 New University Presses Established by Libraries ↑

Adema, Janneke, and Birgit Schmidt. "From Service Providers to Content Producers: New Opportunities for Libraries in Collaborative Open Access Book Publishing." *New Review of Academic Librarianship* 16:, supplement 1 (2010): 28-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2010.509542>

Adema, Janneke, and Graham Stone. *Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing*. London: JISC, 2017. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6666/1/Changing-publishing-ecologies-report.pdf>

New university presses and scholarly publishing in the library are increasingly playing an important role in the shift of scholarly communications. The US-based Library Publishing Coalition defines these new library-led presses as a "set of activities led by college and university libraries to support the creation, dissemination, and curation of scholarly, creative, and/or educational works." (Skinner et al., 2014; Library Publishing Coalition, 2013). They typically embrace open access, digital first, new business models, enable universities to meet strategic goals including outreach and impact, and facilitate researchers in publishing research outputs.

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———. "The Surge in New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing: An Overview of a Changing Publishing Ecology in the UK." *LIBER Quarterly* 27, no. 1 (2017): 97-126. <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10856>

This article outlines the rise and development of New University Presses and Academic-Led Presses in the UK or publishing for the UK market. Based on the Jisc research project, *Changing publishing ecologies: a landscape study of new university presses and*

academic-led publishing, commonalities between these two types of presses are identified to better assess their future needs and requirements. Based on this analysis, the article argues for the development of a publishing toolkit, for further research into the creation of a typology of presses and publishing initiatives, and for support with community building to help these initiatives grow and develop further, whilst promoting a more diverse publishing ecology.

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Ayris, Paul. "Open Access E-Books: The Role of the Institution." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 27 (2014): 7-10. <http://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.140>

This article explains the policy position taken by University College London (UCL) in establishing the UCL Press. It sets the creation of the Press against the background of national open access (OA) policy development in the UK. UCL Press, repatriated from a commercial provider, was relaunched as an OA press as part of UCL Library Services on 1 August 2013. The Press will publish both OA electronic journals and OA monographs, with a particular emphasis in the latter on the arts, humanities and social sciences. UCL is largely funding Press activity from its own internal funds, seeing OA as an opportunity rather than a threat.

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Ayris, Paul, and Lara Speicher. "UCL Press: the UK's 'First Fully Open Access' University Press." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 28, no. 3 (2015): 44-50. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.257>

The purpose of this article is to set in context the launch of University College London Press (UCL Press), which describes itself as the UK's first fully open access (OA) university press. The drivers for this launch are bound up with the global movement towards open access and open science—developments in which UCL is acknowledged as a European leader. The first part of the article looks at these movements and relates them to the relaunch in May 2015 of the UCL Press imprint as an OA imprint. This analysis has been undertaken by Dr Paul Ayris, Director of UCL Library Services and Chief Executive of UCL Press.

The second half of the article is a personal account by Lara Speicher, Publishing Manager at UCL Press, of the relaunch of the Press. This section looks at staffing structures, business models, technical infrastructures, publishing programmes and content.

In the final part of the article, Paul Ayris draws some conclusions from the history of the relaunch of UCL Press and sets these in the context of the global open science discussion.

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Bargheer, Margo, and Birgit Schmidt. "Göttingen University Press: Publishing Services in an Open Access Environment." *Information Services & Use* 28, no. 2 (2008): 133-139. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/information-services-and-use/isu569>

Henry, Charles. "Rice University Press: Fons et Origo." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 10, no. 2 (2007). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0010.205>

Lindgren, Birgitta Hellmark. "Sustainable Open Access Publishing: Preconditions, Dialog, and Continuous Adaptation: The Stockholm University Press Case." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.204>

Stockholm University Press opened up for proposals of books and journals in June 2014 followed by a decision by the Vice Chancellor/Provost at Stockholm University. The goal was to start a fully open university press for the dissemination of peer-reviewed books and journals. The library organisation was given the assignment to build a structure for this, with focus on quality assessment and affordable publishing fees. The task was also to

ensure that these structures are sustainable, catered for and encourage ethical publishing practices. The main goal of its operation is to communicate research without paywalls in the most efficient way possible.

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Little, Geoffrey. "Nothing New Under the Sun: Library Publishing and the Concordia University Press." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.205>

The author of *Ecclesiastes* tells us that there is nothing new under the sun.[1] In their excellent 2015 report *The Once and Future Publishing Library*, Ann Okerson and Alex Holzman remind readers that library publishing has a venerable history. Indeed, many of the oldest North American university presses like those at Johns Hopkins, North Carolina, and Toronto were set up by librarians or based in the university library system.[2] Since 2013 we have been working on a project at Concordia University in Montreal to establish a university press that will be based in our library and that will publish peer-reviewed monographs in the humanities, social sciences, and fine arts. Digital editions will be available open access under a creative commons licence, while print books will be simultaneously published where and when appropriate and available for purchase by individual readers and libraries. Authors will be published irrespective of their institutional affiliation. This paper is a brief description of our project that includes an overview of our processes and planning, lessons learned, and next steps in the short and long terms.

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———. "Old Traditions and New Technologies: Creating Concordia University Press." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 49, no. 2 (2018): 213-230. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.49.2.213>

Lockett, Andrew, and Lara Speicher. "New University Presses in the UK: Accessing a Mission." *Learned Publishing* 29, no. s1 (2016): 320-329. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1049>

Meetz, Johanna, and Boczar, Jason. "Library Publishing Programs at Capacity: Addressing Issues of Sustainability and Scalability." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 10, no. 1 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.31274/jlsc.12909>

Introduction: This article discusses the changes to overall goals, direction, and services that were made to two library publishing programs at Pacific University and the University of South Florida when they were no longer able to grow their programs due to an inability to hire additional staff and COVID-19-instigated staff reassignments. Description of Programs: Pacific University's publishing program grew out of its institutional repository and, at its peak, published seven open access journals. In addition, Pacific University Libraries founded a University Press in 2016, which has published six books as of 2021. The University of South Florida's publishing program began publishing open access journals in 2008, and it has grown to include over 20 journals. Lessons Learned: Both the Pacific University and the University of South Florida publishing programs have faced scalability and sustainability issues, which were further exacerbated by COVID-19. The focus of our library publishing programs, as well as many others, has been on continual growth, which is not sustainable without the ability to hire additional staff or allocate staff time differently. We argue that standardizing services as well as creating a business plan can help ensure that publishing programs are sustainable and scalable. Next Steps: We hope to begin a conversation among library publishers about acknowledging limits and creating achievable definitions of success outside of continual growth.

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Mercieca, Paul. "'Integration and Collaboration' within Recently Established Australian Scholarly Publishing Initiatives." *OCLC Systems & Services* 2, no. 3 (2006): 149-154. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10650750610686180>

Missingham, Roxanne, and Lorena Kanellopoulos. "A Decade of Change: Running a University E-press." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 121-126. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013. <http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Montgomery, Lucy, Cameron Neylon, Alkim Ozaygen, and Tama Leaver. "Getting the Best Out of Data for Open Access Monograph Presses: A Case Study of UCL Press." *Learned Publishing* 31, no. 4 (2018): 335-344. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1168>

Moody, Fred. "Rice University Press: Nascentis Fame." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 16, no. 1 (2013). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0016.102>

Rice University Press (RUP), which began full operation in February 2007, proved a short-lived experiment. After three years of supporting one paid staff position and modest additional funding for contracted book design work, office expenses, and travel,[1] Rice closed the press down as part of a larger, campuswide, budget-cutting effort. Faced with a choice between investing more financial and human capital in its press as a condition for gaining substantial foundation support or opting out of the experiment altogether, university administration chose the latter.

Short-lived as the RUP experience was, it nevertheless offers some important lessons for people pondering the future of academic publishing and its inexorable move in a digital direction. There is no question that traditional printed-on-paper publishing is dying out and that it will be replaced by digital academic discourse distributed on a different economic model. There are, however, substantial questions about when and how this paradigm shift will come about, and the Rice University Press story may offer some answers.

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Mrva-Montoya, Agata. "Open Access Strategy for a 'New' University Press: A View through the Stakeholder Lens." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 48, no. 4 (2017): 221-242. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.48.4.221>

Sisättö, Outi, Kati Mäki, anja Heikkilä, and Jane Katjavivi. "University Presses and University Libraries as Publishers: New Models and Benefits." In *Empowering People: Collaboration between Finnish and Namibian University Libraries*, 250-269. Tampere, Finland: Tampere University Press. 2012. <http://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi:uta-201304081078>

Stone, Graham. "Sustaining the Growth of Library Scholarly Publishing in a New University Press." *Information Services & Use* 36, no. 3-4 (2016): 147-158. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-160812>

Taylor, Megan. "Mapping the Publishing Challenges for an Open Access University Press." *Publications* 7, no. 4 (2019): 63. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7040063>

Managing a New University Press (NUP) is often a one-person operation and, with limits on time and resources, efficiency and effectiveness are key to having a successful production process and providing a high level of author, editor and reader services. This article looks at the challenges faced by open access (OA) university presses throughout the publishing journey and considers ways in which these challenges can be addressed. In particular, the article focuses on six key stages throughout the lifecycle of an open access publication: commissioning; review; production; discoverability; marketing; analytics. Approached from the point of view of the University of Huddersfield Press, this article also draws on discussions and experiences of other NUPs from community-led forums and events. By highlighting the issues faced, and the potential solutions to them, this research recognises the need for a tailored and formalised production workflow within NUPs and also provides guidance how to begin implementing possible solutions.

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Taylor, Megan, and Kathrine S. H. Jensen. "Developing a Model for University Presses." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 32, no. 1 (2019): p.19. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.469>

This article presents a model for developing a university press based around three guiding principles and six key stages of the publishing process, with associated activities. The model is designed to be applicable to a range of business models, including subscription, open access and hybrid. The guiding principles, publishing stages and strategic points all constitute the building blocks necessary to implement and maintain a sustainable university press. At the centre of the model there are three interconnected main guiding principles: strategic alignment, stakeholder relationships and demonstrating impact. The publishing process outlined in the outer ring of the model is made up of six sections: editorial, production, dissemination, preservation, communication and analytics. These sections were based on the main stages that a journal article or monograph goes through from proposal or commissioning stage through to publication and beyond. The model highlights the overall importance of working in partnership and building relationships as key to developing and maintaining a successful press.

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———. "Engaging and Supporting a University Press Scholarly Community." *Publications* 6, no. 2 (2018): 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications6020013>

In this paper we explore how the development of The University of Huddersfield Press, a publisher of open access scholarly journals and monographs, has enabled the sharing of research with a wider online audience. We situate the development of the Press within a wider research environment and growing community of New University Presses (NUPs) where there is an increasing demand for demonstrating research impact, which drives the need for improved analysis and reporting of impact data, a task that often falls within the remit of library and academic support services. We detail the benefits of the University Press Manager role in terms of ensuring professional service that delivers consistency and sustainability. We go on to outline the experiences of engaging with different online spaces and detail the extensive support for student authors. We argue that in order for the Press to support building a strong and engaged scholarly community and provide new spaces for emerging research, continued investment in both platform development and infrastructure is required.

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4.0 Library and Traditional University Press Mergers/Partnerships ↑

Association of American University Presses. *Library-Press Collaboration Survey*: New York Association of American University Presses, 2013.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20200221162909/http://www.aupresses.org/resources/for-members/data-collection-and-analysis/library-press-collaboration-survey>

Bains, Simon. "The Role of the Library in Scholarly Publishing: The University of Manchester Experience." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 39, no. 3 (2017): 70-77.

<http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.380>

The emergence of networked digital methods of scholarly dissemination has transformed the role of the academic library in the context of the research life cycle. It now plays an important role in the dissemination of research outputs (e.g. through repository management and gold open access publication processing) as well as more traditional acquisition and collection management. The University of Manchester Library and Manchester University Press have developed a strategic relationship to consider how they can work in partnership to support new approaches to scholarly publishing. They have delivered two projects to understand researcher and student needs and to develop tools and services to meet these needs. This work has found that the creation of new journal titles is costly and provides significant resourcing challenges and that support for student journals in particular is mixed amongst senior academic administrators. Research has suggested that there is more value to the University in the provision of training in scholarly

publishing than in the creation of new in-house journal titles. Where such titles are created, careful consideration of sustainable business models is vital.

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Bakker, Caitlin. "Bringing History into the Digital Age: A Case Study of an Online Journal Transition." *Serials Librarian* 64, no. 1-4 (2013): 263-266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2013.760419>

Barake, Sarah Roughley, and Alison Welsby. "Collaboration across Campus: Open Monograph Insights from a Library and 'Old' University Press Partnership." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 34, no. 1 (2021): 2. <https://doi.org/10.1629/UKSG.533>

Liverpool University Press and the University of Liverpool Library collaborated to publish two open access monographs to gain insights into each other's processes and requirements, and improve the guidance provided to researchers and authors. Lessons learned include researchers' knowledge of publishing and open access, the monograph publishing process and costs involved, licences and third-party content and the marketing and discoverability of open monographs. Researchers, particularly those at the start of their career, may not have much knowledge and experience of publishing and so it is important for publishers to be as transparent as possible about the processes involved, and for libraries to ensure they are providing sufficient guidance. Knowledge about publishers' processes and costs allows libraries to have a better understanding about what is reasonable to expect and for researchers to better plan costs for funding applications. Transparency from publishers about the types of costs involved, as well as a greater understanding of the financial requirements of libraries and their institutions, will allow publishers to plan their marketing of open monographs more effectively. The project demonstrated that collaboration between libraries and publishers can be extremely valuable and beneficial to both.

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Barker, Andrew. "The Institution as E-textbook Publisher." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 28, no. 3 (2015): 51-55. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.265>

Providing students with sufficient copies of core textbooks is an increasing challenge in an age of ever higher fees, economic realities and heightened student expectations regarding provision of library resources. This article outlines the partnership between the University of Liverpool Library and Liverpool University Press (LUP), which has progressed from the creation of a library advisory board to the co-creation of two bespoke and open access (OA) e-textbooks as part of a Jisc-funded project. It tells the story of why we have gone down this route at Liverpool and what we hope to gain from the creation of these e-textbooks.

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Chadwell, Faye A., and Dianna M Fisher. "Creating Open Textbooks: A Unique Partnership between Oregon State University Libraries and Press and Open Oregon State." *Open Praxis* 8, no. 2 (2016): 123–130. <http://doi.org/10.5944/openpraxis.8.2.290>

This article presents Oregon State University's experience launching an innovative Open Textbook initiative in spring 2014. The partners, Open Oregon State and the Oregon State University Libraries and Press, aimed to reduce the cost of course materials for students while ensuring the content created was peer-reviewed and employed multimedia capabilities. This initiative sought to showcase existing and emerging disciplinary strengths of the University thus creating unique course content that could be shared globally. This article briefly describes the U.S. landscape for open textbook creation and adoption. It demonstrates how this unique partnership has developed, covering barriers and benefits, and what the future could hold for new projects.

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Clement, Richard W. "Library and University Press Integration: A New Vision for University Publishing." *Journal of Library Administration* 51, no. 5-6 (2011): 507-528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2011.589330>

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Crow, Raym. *Campus-Based Publishing Partnerships: A Guide to the Critical Issues*. Washington, DC: SPARC, 2009. <https://web.archive.org/web/20090329103546/http://www.arl.org/sparc/partnering/guide/>

Eaton, Nancy, Bonnie MacEwan, Peter Potter. "Learning to Work Together: The Libraries and the University Press at Penn State." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 35, no. 4 (2004): 215-220. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.35.4.215>

Horava, Tony. "Making OA Monographs Happen: Library-Press Collaboration at the University of Ottawa, Canada." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 29, no. 1 (2016): 57-63. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.278>

At the University of Ottawa, Canada, the UO Press and the UO Library have developed a strategic partnership to publish and disseminate selected new monographs as gold open access (OA). Starting in 2013, the Library agreed to fund three books at C\$10,000 per book (a total of C\$30,000 per year) in order to remove barriers to accessing scholarship and to align with scholarly communication goals of the University. In 2015 this agreement was renewed for another three years and the funding was increased to cover four books (a total of C\$40,000 per year). Ten titles have so far been published under this model. The data reveals that there have been 12,629 downloads as well as 16,584 page views of these titles, as of September 2015. There have been over 4,700 copies (print and EPUB) sold in spite of the free availability of the PDF version. This program has been very successful in terms of increasing the visibility and impact of the Press's publications; in providing unrestricted access to new scholarly research; and also in providing a significant source of revenue for the Press. The goals, process and outcomes are described in the context of the UO Press and the UO Library.

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Li, Yuan, Suzanne E. Guidod, and Suzanne Preate. "A Case Study in Open Access Journal Publishing at Syracuse University: Library and University Press Partnership Furthers Scholarly Communications." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 215-221. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013. <http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Li, Yuan, Sarah Kalikman Lippincott, Sarah Hare, Jamie Wittenberg, Suzanne M. Preate, Amanda Page, and Suzanne E. Guidod. "The Library-Press Partnership: An Overview and Two Case Studies." *Library Trends* 67, no. 2 (2018): 319-34. <https://doi.org/10.1353/LIB.2018.0039>

McCormick, Monica. "Learning to Say Maybe: Building NYU's Press/Library Collaboration." *Against the Grain* 20, no. 6 (2008): Article 8. <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/atg/vol20/iss6/8/>

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Roh, Charlotte. "Library-Press Collaborations: A Study Taken on Behalf of the University of Arizona." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1102. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1102>

BACKGROUND The University of Arizona Press moved under the University of Arizona Library both physically and administratively a few years ago, echoing a trend amongst university presses: 20 AAUP members now are under the administration of university libraries. To understand the new evolving relationships in scholarly communication, a review of university press and library collaborations was undertaken by the University of Arizona Press and the University of Arizona Library through the Association of Research Libraries Career Enhancement Program (ARL CEP). **LITERATURE REVIEW** There has been much written throughout the years on both the acrimonious and collaborative relationships between university presses and academic libraries. Much of the literature includes either editorials or case studies, with one or two major reviews of scholarly communications and the state of publishing. **DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT** During the course of nine weeks, the ARL CEP Fellow reviewed existing literature, interviewed staff at the University of Arizona Press and Library, and conducted 27 informal interviews with library deans, press directors, and scholarly communications leaders. The interviews addressed the partnership history, structure, motivations, goals and needs, administrative support and budget decisions, key stakeholders, and thoughts on the future of their relationships as well as scholarly communications. Then University of Arizona Library and Press staff were interviewed regarding their perceptions of their roles and each other's roles. **NEXT STEPS** This research report includes findings from the literature review and interviews as well as specific recommendations for the University of Arizona that will be implemented to improve and build relationships going forward.

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Shearer, Kathleen. *A Review of Emerging Models in Canadian Academic Publishing*. Toronto: University of British Columbia Library, 2010. <http://hdl.handle.net/2429/24008>

Spooner, Michael, and Andrew Wesolek. "A Case Study of Bringing an Institutional Repository and a University Press Together." In *Library Publishing Toolkit*, ed. Allison Brown, 153-160. Geneseo: IDS Project Press, 2013. <http://idsproject.org/press/LibraryPublishingToolkit.aspx>

Staines, Heather. "Mission Alignment: University Presses versus Institutional Visions." *Learned Publishing* 34, no. 2 (2021): 272-278. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1346>

Stapleton Suzanne Cady. "A Team Approach: Library Publishing Partnerships with Scholarly Societies." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2326>

INTRODUCTION The journal publishing service at the University of Florida George A. Smathers Libraries is structured to use a team-based approach that integrates subject specialists across the library. **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM** Since 2012, the UF Libraries have worked in partnership with a number of scholarly societies to publish their research. The focus, to date, of academic library publishing on institutional publications belies potential partnerships with scholarly societies and organizations external to the library's institution. Services provided, challenges faced, and examples of successful publishing partnerships with UF Libraries are described. The team approach enables the library to be innovative and nimble in response to publishing opportunities. Scholarly societies most interested in entering publishing contracts with the Libraries publishing program are those

that share aspects of the library mission such as accessibility and innovation. NEXT STEPS Academic library publishing offers unique partnership opportunities for scholarly societies and external organizations that are mutually beneficial and that complement library publishing of institutional material.

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Sutton, Shan C, and Faye A Chadwell. "Open Textbooks at Oregon State University: A Case Study of New Opportunities for Academic Libraries and University Presses." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1174. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1174>

INTRODUCTION This article describes a joint open textbook publishing initiative begun in 2013 between Oregon State University (OSU) Libraries and Press and the Open Educational Resources and Emerging Technologies unit of Oregon State University's Extended Campus. **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM** This initiative combines the Open Access values and project management resources of OSU Libraries, the book production (peer review, editing, design, marketing) expertise of OSU Press, and the technological development skills of the Open Educational Resources and Emerging Technologies unit. Authored by OSU faculty and focused across some of the University's signature areas, the initiative seeks to establish a sustainable model for research libraries and university presses to collaborate with each other and other partners to publish open textbooks that will benefit students on both economic and educational levels. The article analyzes how open textbooks fit within the emerging library publishing movement, examines the implementation of the OSU open textbook publishing initiative, and conveys some lessons learned for other libraries to consider as they entertain the possibility of similar collaborations. **NEXT STEPS** A description of next steps includes tracking course adoptions of the textbooks as well as establishing sustainable digital publishing platforms and business models.

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Taylor, Donald, Heather Morrison, Brian Owen, Kumiko Vézina, and Andrew Waller. "Open Access Publishing in Canada: Current and Future Library and University Press Supports." *Publications* 1, no. 1 (2013): 27-48. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PUBLICATIONS1010027>

Canadian university libraries, Canadian university presses, and non-university scholarly presses at Canadian universities were surveyed in the first part of 2010 as to the level of their support of Open Access (OA) journal publishing. Respondents were asked about journal hosting services in their organization as well as their thoughts on internal and external support for open access publishing. Results showed that most of the organizations are hosting OA journals, largely between one and five in number, and many supply journal hosting services, including some technical support. Personnel resources are a notable factor in the ability to host journals. Most respondents engage in some sort of internal support for open access publishing and are open to options that they are presently not utilizing. They are particularly amenable to OA publishing support from outside of their organizations, especially assistance at a consortial level.

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Taylor, Laurie N., Brian W. Keith, Chelsea Dinsmore, and Meredith Morris-Babb. *SPEC Kit 357: Libraries, Presses, and Publishing*. Washington, DC: ARL, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.29242/spec.357>

Thatcher Sanford, G. "Open-Access Monograph Publishing and the Origins of the Office of Digital Scholarly Publishing at Penn State University." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 46, no. 3 (2015): 203-223. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.46.3.01>

Tsoukala, Victoria. *University-Based Open Access Publishing: State of Play*. Apeldoorn: SPARC Europe, 2015.

https://web.archive.org/web/20160514024625/http://sparceurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/SE_UPublishing_Report_0315.pdf

This report, prepared for SPARC Europe, sketches the landscape of university-based not-for-profit publishing in Europe with a primary focus on open access publishing of journals. It provides a view of the different types of initiatives in terms of their size, operational and business models, technologies used, stakeholder involvement, concentration of scientific fields, growth, as well as regional characteristics and recommendations for SPARC Europe and DOAJ.

The report attests to a rich and continuously evolving ecology of open access publishing initiatives in universities in Europe and elsewhere. Beyond the commercial publishing models, it appears that university libraries are largely the foci of intense activity in journal publishing and books (primarily where a university press exists), while national governments are moving towards building national collections, national portals and services paid for by public funds to make research published within the country more relevant and accessible internationally. This ecology is primarily populated by small publishers who are largely invisible, and much smaller numbers of large and medium-sized university-based activities. At the same time, a growing number of innovative initiatives in the University and outside, mostly initiated by scholars and University Presses, eager to experiment in developing a fair and sustainable scholarly communications system, attests to a vibrant and swiftly-evolving landscape.

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Waller, Mira, William M. Cross, and Lillian Rigling. "The Open Textbook Toolkit: Seeding Successful Partnerships for Collaboration between Academic Libraries and University Presses." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 49, no. 1 (2017): 53-65. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.49.1.53>

Ward, Monica, and Joanie Lavoie. "A Library-Publisher Partnership for Open Access: Building an Innovative Relationship between Scholarly Publishers and Academic Libraries." *LIBER Quarterly* 25, no. 4 (2016): 189-204. <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10139>

This article presents an overview of a strategic partnership undertaken by the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN) and the Érudit Consortium (Érudit) to support the move towards open access for Canadian francophone scholarly journals.

CRKN and Érudit have had a relationship through a traditional commercial subscription model since 2008. In 2014, the two organizations recognized the need for a new relationship that would address two major challenges: the fragility of the Canadian not-for-profit scholarly publishing environment and the increasing pressure from libraries and funding agencies for scholarly journals to move towards open access. Érudit and CRKN have worked collaboratively to create an innovative partnership, which provides a framework for a new relationship between publishers and libraries, and helps to provide financial support to Canadian publishers during the transition to a fully open access model.

This paper presents the perspectives of the two organizations involved in the partnership by outlining the common goals, objectives, and strategy, as well as the differing needs and perspectives of libraries and publishers. It summarizes the key aspects of the partnership as well as the challenges faced. Through this case study, the authors demonstrate how university libraries can play an active role in working with journals to support open access to research.

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Watkinson, Charles. "From Collaboration to Integration University Presses and Libraries." In *Getting the Word Out: Academic Libraries as Scholarly Publishers*, ed. Maria Bonn and Mike Furlough, 83-112. Chicago: Association of College and Research Libraries, 2015. <https://bit.ly/3AQ5tPu>

University presses and academic libraries should be natural allies in the quest to create a more equitable scholarly publishing system. Expert in scholarly information management, situated on university and college campuses, supported to a varying degree by the same funding sources, and sharing many philosophical ideals, librarians and university press publishers seem to be logical partners. However, until very recently, examples of successful press/library collaboration in the production of knowledge have been lacking. This chapter surveys such collaboration initiatives and proposes a taxonomy of types, identifies some of the challenges that exist for institutions wishing to forge closer alliances, and explores the opportunities that such campus publishing partnerships are presenting for the respective partners, for their parent institutions, and for the scholars and other publics they ultimately exist to serve.

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———. "Why Marriage Matters: A North American Perspective on Press/Library Partnerships." *Learned Publishing* 29, no. S1 (2016): 342-347. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1044>

- Around 30% of campus-based members of the Association of American University Presses now report to libraries, more than double the number 5 years ago.
- Beyond reporting relationships, physical collocation and joint strategic planning characterize the most integrated press/library partnerships.
- The main mutual advantages of deep press/library collaboration are economic efficiency, greater relevance to parent institutions, and an increased capacity to engage with the changing needs of authors in the digital age.
- There is emerging interest in collaboration at scale among libraries and presses that may extend the impact of press/library collaboration beyond single institutions.

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Wittenberg, Kate. "The Electronic Publishing Initiative at Columbia (EPIC): A University-Based Collaboration in Digital Scholarly Communication." *Learned Publishing* 14, no. 1 (2001): 29-32. <https://doi.org/10.1087/09531510125100241>

5.0 Technical Publishing Infrastructure ↑

Altman, Micah, Eleni Castro, Mercè Crosas, Philip Durbin, Alex Garnett, and Jen Whitney. "Open Journal Systems and Dataverse Integration—Helping Journals to Upgrade Data Publication for Reusable Research." *Code4Lib Journal*, no. 30 (2015). <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/10989>

This article describes the novel open source tools for open data publication in open access journal workflows. This comprises a plugin for Open Journal Systems that supports a data submission, citation, review, and publication workflow; and an extension to the Dataverse system that provides a standard deposit API. We describe the function and design of these tools, provide examples of their use, and summarize their initial reception. We conclude by discussing future plans and potential impact.

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Bankier, Jean-Gabriel, and Irene Perciali. "The Institutional Repository Rediscovered: What Can a University Do for Open Access Publishing?" *Serials Review* 34, no. 1 (2008): 21-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2008.10765147>

Barnes, Sherri. "The Community-Led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) Project: A Transformative Open Access Monograph Initiative." *College & Research Libraries News* 81, no. 11 (2020): 534-537. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.81.11.534>

Bernhardt, Beth R. "Library Roles in Supporting Creation of Serials: Open Journal Systems at The University of North Carolina at Greensboro." *Serials Review* 42, no. 3 (2016): 240-242. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2016.1204204>

Bertino, Andrea C., and Heather Staines. "Enabling A Conversation Across Scholarly Monographs through Open Annotation." *Publications* 7, no. 2 (2019): 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PUBLICATIONS7020041>

The digital format opens up new possibilities for interaction with monographic publications. In particular, annotation tools make it possible to broaden the discussion on the content of a book, to suggest new ideas, to report errors or inaccuracies, and to conduct open peer reviews. However, this requires the support of the users who might not yet be familiar with the annotation of digital documents. This paper will give concrete examples and recommendations for exploiting the potential of annotation in academic research and teaching. After presenting the annotation tool of Hypothesis, the article focuses on its use in the context of HIRMEOS (High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science Infrastructure), a project aimed to improve the Open Access digital monograph. The general line and the aims of a post-peer review experiment with the annotation tool, as well as its usage in didactic activities concerning monographic publications are presented and proposed as potential best practices for similar annotation activities

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Borchard, Laurie, Michael Biondo, Stephen Kutay, David Morck, and Andrew Philip Weiss. "Making Journals Accessible Front & Back: Examining Open Journal Systems at CSU Northridge." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 1 (2015): 35-50. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0013>

Büttner, Alexandra, Sabine Gehrlein, and Stefanie Clormann. "Online Survey on Open Journal Systems in Germany and the Network OJS-de.net." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 7, no. 1 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2016v7n1a240>

Castro, Eleni, and Alex Garnett. "Building a Bridge Between Journal Articles and Research Data: The PKP-Dataverse Integration Project." *International Journal of Digital Curation* 9, no. 1 (2014): 176-184. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v9i1.311>

A growing number of funding agencies and international scholarly organizations are requesting that research data be made more openly available to help validate and advance scientific research. Thus, this is an opportune moment for research data repositories to partner with journal editors and publishers in order to simplify and improve data curation and publishing practices. One practical example of this type of cooperation is currently being facilitated by a two year (2012-2014) one million dollar Sloan Foundation grant, integrating two well-established open source systems: the Public Knowledge Project's (PKP) Open Journal Systems (OJS), developed by Stanford University and Simon Fraser University; and Harvard University's Dataverse Network web application, developed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS). To help make this interoperability possible, an OJS Dataverse plugin and Data Deposit API are being developed, which together will allow authors to submit their articles and datasets through an existing journal management interface, while the underlying data are seamlessly deposited into a research data repository, such as the Harvard Dataverse. This practice paper will provide an overview of the project, and a brief exploration of some of the specific challenges to and advantages of this integration.

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Czyk, Mark, and Sayeed Choudhury. "A Survey and Evaluation of Open-Source Electronic Publishing Systems." (2008). <http://jhir.library.jhu.edu/handle/1774.2/32737>

Daly, Rebecca, and Michael Organ. "Research Online: Digital Commons as a Publishing Platform at the University of Wollongong, Australia." *Serials Review* 35, no. 3 (2009): 149-

153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2009.10765233>

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Eikebrokk, Trude, Aysa Ekanger, Katherine Fonn, Jan Erik Frantsvåg, and Obiajulu Odu. "Some Highlights from the PKP 2019 International Scholarly Publishing Conference." *Nordic Perspectives on Open Science* 4 (December 30, 2019). <https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/nopos/article/view/5204>.

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Bearing these considerations in mind, the Centre for Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London embarked upon building a journal submission and hosting platform, Janeway, learning from our experiences of running the Open Library of Humanities (OLH). We knew Open Journal Systems (OJS) well at this time, but were not big fans of PHP, the language in which it is written. We also were aware of the work being done by Coko (the Collaborative Knowledge Foundation) in Node.js. What we really craved, though, was a scholarly communications platform written in Python/Django. This was not just a language preference but was also linked to issues around hiring and simplicity, as mentioned above. Python was the most popular programming language in 2017, which would mean that a platform in this language would be comprehensible to a wide range of programmers. So, we chose to write in Python using the Django framework, since this is a well-known, stable, and secure framework for the development of web applications. The platform's ongoing development is funded by a combination of revenue streams: from the OLH, which has begun using the platform as part of a mixed economy of suppliers, and from hosting services that we are providing to others.

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The Indiana University (IU) Libraries have a long history of using the TEI markup standard to encode and publish electronic texts, but choosing the best publishing platform has been challenging for certain projects. Before formally launching an open access journal publishing program in 2008, the Libraries collaborated with two scholarly journals to provide open access publishing using P3 SGML and P4 XML TEI encoding delivered through the DSpace and XTF platforms. Both journals used complex encoding, transformation, and delivery workflows that required copious amounts of custom software development to function properly. As these systems aged, the time and effort required to maintain them steadily increased. In 2013, the Libraries began planning to migrate these journals into the Open Journal Systems (OJS)1 platform while preserving the TEI markup.

Both journals are now publishing using the OJS platform. The *Indiana Magazine of History*² was successfully launched in OJS in August 2014, and The *Medieval Review*³ was launched in June 2015. Publishing in this manner leverages the IU Libraries' strengths in electronic text projects and XML workflows within an easy-to-use, flexible platform that

journal editors appreciate. The success of these migrations presents a new framework for future XML publishing of open access journals at Indiana University.

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It is increasingly necessary for researchers in all fields to write computer code, and in order to reproduce research results, it is important that this code is published. We present Jupyter notebooks, a document format for publishing code, results and explanations in a form that is both readable and executable. We discuss various tools and use cases for notebook documents.

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From June 2017 to August 2018, Scholars Portal, a consortial service of the Ontario Council of University Libraries, upgraded 10 different multi-journal instances of the Open Journal Systems (OJS) 3 software, building expertise on the upgrade process along the way. The final and the largest instance to be upgraded was the University of Toronto Libraries, which hosts over 50 journals. In this article, we will discuss the upgrade planning and process, problems encountered along the way, and some best practices in supporting journal teams through the upgrade on a multi-journal instance. We will also include checklists and technical troubleshooting tips to help institutions make their upgrade as

smooth and worry-free as possible. Finally, we will go over post-upgrade support strategies and next steps in making the most out of your transition to OJS 3.

This article will primarily be useful for institutions hosting instances of OJS 2, but those that have already upgraded, or are considering hosting the software, may find the outlined approach to support and testing helpful.

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Maxwell, John W., Erik Hanson, Leena Desai, Carmen Tiampo, Kim O'Donnell, Avvai Ketheeswaran, Melody Sun, Emma Walter, and Ellen Michelle. *Mind the Gap: A Landscape Analysis of Open Source Publishing Tools and Platforms*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2019. <https://assets.pubpub.org/z1qjpyk6/01566244075411.pdf>

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In January 2009, the Colorado Association of Libraries (CAL) suspended publication of its print quarterly journal, *Colorado Libraries*, as a cost-saving measure in a time of fiscal uncertainty. Printing and mailing the journal to its 1300 members cost CAL more than \$26,000 per year. Publication of the journal was placed on an indefinite hiatus until the editorial staff proposed an online, open access format a year later. The benefits to migrating to open access included: significantly lower costs; a green platform; instant availability of content; a greater level of access to users with disabilities; and a higher level of visibility of the journal and the association. The editorial staff chose Drupal, including the E-journal module, and while Drupal is notorious for its steep learning curve—which exacerbated delays to content that had been created before the publishing hiatus—the fourth electronic issue was published recently at coloradolibrariesjournal.org. This article will discuss both the benefits and challenges of transitioning to an open access model and the choice Drupal as a platform over other more established journal software options.

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This is a story about how an Open Journal Systems-based library publishing service tried (and failed) to implement XML in one of its publications. We ran a small project to look at how journals we support could develop a JATS XML-based publishing workflow using existing open software tools.

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Ratan, Kristen, Katherine Skinner, Catherine Mitchell, Brandon Locke, and David Pcolar. *Library Publishing Infrastructure: Assembling New Solutions*. Atlanta: Educopia Institute, 2021. <https://educopia.org/nglp-lib-pub-infrastructure/>

This report documents the design, methods, results, and recommendations of the Next Generation Library Publishing (NGLP) project team's 2019-2021 study of library publishing infrastructure gaps and requirements. This research was designed to accomplish two related goals: 1) to reveal and chronicle library publishing stakeholders' current needs, interests, and desires regarding the tools and environments that support their publishing activities, and 2) to develop a meta-understanding of the open-source tools and environments available for publishing, how those tools and environments might be combined and built upon, and where gaps between them might be mitigated through standards, scripts, and documentation.

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The explosive growth of computational notebooks provides a unique opportunity to support computational research, but care must be taken when performing and sharing analyses in notebooks. Given these opportunities and challenges, we have compiled a set of rules, tips, tools, and example notebooks to help guide Jupyter Notebook authors. While we focus on a few core uses of Jupyter Notebooks observed in our own research, many of these rules can be applied to other computational notebooks and use cases. . . . Whether you use notebooks to track preliminary analyses, to present polished results to collaborators, as finely tuned pipelines for recurring analyses, or for all of the above, following this advice will help you write and share analyses that are easier to read, run, and explore.

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About the Author ↑

Charles W. Bailey, Jr. is the publisher of [Digital Scholarship](#) and a noncommercial digital artist (ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8453-4402>).

Bailey has over 45 years of information technology, digital publishing, and instructional technology experience, including 24 years of managerial experience in academic libraries. From 2004 to 2007, he was the Assistant Dean for Digital Library Planning and Development at the University of Houston Libraries. From 1987 to 2003, he served as Assistant Dean/Director for Systems at the University of Houston Libraries.

Previously, he served as Head, Systems and Research Services at the Health Sciences Library, The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; Systems Librarian at the Milton S. Eisenhower Library, The Johns Hopkins University; User Documentation Specialist at the OCLC Online Computer Library Center; and Media Library Manager at the Learning Resources Center, SUNY College at Oswego.

Bailey has discussed his career in an [interview](#) in *Preservation, Digital Technology & Culture*. See [Bailey's vita](#) for more details.

Bailey has been an open access publisher for over 33 years. In 1989, Bailey established [PACS-L](#), a discussion list about public-access computers in libraries, and [The Public-](#)

Access Computer Systems Review, the first open access journal in the field of library and information science. He served as PACS-L Moderator until November 1991 and as Editor-in-Chief of *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review* until the end of 1996.

In 1990, Bailey and Dana Rooks established *Public-Access Computer Systems News*, an electronic newsletter, and Bailey co-edited this publication until 1992.

In 1992, he founded the PACS-P mailing list for announcing the publication of selected e-serials, and he moderated this list until 2007.

In 1996, he established the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography (SEPB)*, an open access book that was updated 80 times by 2011.

In 2001, he added the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Weblog*, which announced relevant new publications, to *SEPB*. It was published through 2013.

In 2001, he was selected as a team member of *Current Cites*, and he has been a frequent contributor of reviews to this monthly e-serial until 2020.

In 2005, he published the *Open Access Bibliography: Liberating Scholarly Literature with E-prints and Open Access Journals* with the Association of Research Libraries (also a website).

In 2005, Bailey established Digital Scholarship (<http://digital-scholarship.org/>), which provides information and commentary about digital copyright, digital curation, digital repository, open access, research data management, scholarly communication, and other digital information issues. Digital Scholarship's digital publications are open access. Its publications are under Creative Commons licenses.

At that time, he also established *DigitalKoans*, a weblog that covers the same topics as Digital Scholarship.

From April 2005 through March 2023, Bailey published the following books and book supplements: the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography: 2008 Annual Edition* (2009), *Digital Scholarship 2009* (2010), *Transforming Scholarly Publishing through Open Access: A Bibliography* (2010), the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography 2010* (2011), the *Digital Curation and Preservation Bibliography 2010* (2011), the *Institutional Repository and ETD Bibliography 2011* (2011), the *Digital Curation Bibliography: Preservation and Stewardship of Scholarly Works* (2012), the *Digital Curation Bibliography: Preservation and Stewardship of Scholarly Works, 2012 Supplement* (2013), and the *Research Data Curation and Management Bibliography* (2021).

He also published and updated the following bibliographies and webliographies as websites with links to freely available works: the *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography* (1996-2011), the *Electronic Theses and Dissertations Bibliography* (2005-2021), the *Google Books Bibliography* (2005-2011), the *Institutional Repository Bibliography* (2009-2011), the *Open Access Journals Bibliography* (2010), the *Digital Curation and Preservation Bibliography* (2010-2011), the *E-science and Academic Libraries Bibliography* (2011), the *Digital Curation Resource Guide* (2012), the *Research Data Curation Bibliography* (2012-2019), the *Altmetrics Bibliography* (2013), the *Transforming Peer Review Bibliography* (2014), the *Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography* (2018-2023), the *Research Data Sharing and Reuse Bibliography* (2021), and the *Research Data Publication and Citation Bibliography* (2022).

In 2011, he established the LinkedIn Digital Curation Group.

In 2010, Bailey was given a Best Content by an Individual Award by *The Charleston Advisor*. In 2003, he was named as one of *Library Journal's* "Movers & Shakers." In 1993, he was awarded the first LITA/Library Hi Tech Award For Outstanding Communication for Continuing Education in Library and Information Science. In 1992, Bailey received a Network Citizen Award from the Apple Library.

In 1973, Bailey won a [Wallace Stevens Poetry Award](#). He is the author of *The Cave of Hypnos: Early Poems*, which includes several poems that won that award.

Bailey has written [over 30 papers](#) about artificial intelligence, digital copyright, institutional repositories, open access, scholarly communication, and other topics.

He has served on the editorial boards of *Information Technology and Libraries*, *Library Software Review*, and *Reference Services Review*. He was the founding Vice-Chairperson of the [LITA Imagineering Interest Group](#).

Bailey is a [digital artist](#), and he has made [over 680 digital artworks](#) freely available on social media sites, such as [Flickr](#), under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial licenses. A [list of his artworks that includes links to high resolution JPEG images](#) on Flickr is available.

He holds master's degrees in information and library science and instructional media and technology.

You can contact him at: [publisher at digital-scholarship.org](mailto:publisher@digital-scholarship.org).

You can follow Bailey at these URLs:

Digital Artist weblog: <https://charleswbaileyjr.name> and RSS feed (<https://charleswbaileyjr.name/feed>)

DigitalKoans weblog: <http://digital-scholarship.org/digitalkoans/> and and RSS feed <https://digital-scholarship.org/digitalkoans/feed/>

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Bailey, Charles W., Jr. *Research Data Publication and Citation Bibliography*, version 3. Houston: Digital Scholarship, 2023. <https://digital-scholarship.org//alsp/alsp.htm>.

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